

Survey paper

A survey on 5G private and B5G network threats and safeguarding AI-based security mechanisms through the layered analysis

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ABSTRACT

The fifth-generation (5G) mobile network has shifted the paradigm in connectivity, high-speed data transmission, ultra-low latency, ultra-high throughput, multisense transmission, and ultra-high reliability. Today, industries are increasingly adopting 5G private networks, which also handle sensitive data related to business information, trade secrets, and personal data. Attacks on 5G private networks can potentially result in losing a competitive advantage since different security threats and vulnerabilities progressively target these networks. The unique infrastructure of the 5G network architecture and key enabling technologies exposes them to various vulnerabilities that attackers can target to breach sensitive data, steal information, and disrupt critical systems. Therefore, paying special attention to the security issues of 5G private networks is essential. The advancement of future wireless technology came about because of the different and diverse nature of connected devices, in contrast to the previous generation of mobile networks. The B5G network provides support to open network platforms, open interfaces, and the integration of different key enabling technologies helps manage network services and deploy new services needed for diverse requirements. At the same time, it has increased the attack surface compared to previous-generation networks. Therefore, it is imperative to conduct a review that focuses on addressing and classifying the different emerging threats in the private 5G and B5G networks in a distinctive way. In this paper, we have adopted a layered architecture from an industrial use case of 5G private networks to identify and classify different threats in 5G private networks. The study also characterized and modeled the different threats using information on the type of attack, entry points, and impact of the attack on the architecture layer. Moreover, an analysis of key enablers in 5G private and B5G networks and information on security threats and cyber-attacks is also presented. To accommodate the emerging threats in next-generation wireless technology, we have classified and modeled the different threats in the B5G domain using the common involved layer, which includes perception, network, and application layers in Hexa-x E2E and 6G IoT-enabled architecture. Organizations and projects that do not actively engage in cutting-edge technologies will lose their competitive advantage in the evolving technological landscape. This study has mapped the identified threat categories with different types of threats that could occur at different layers and assessed the entry points of the attacker. We have also identified the attack's impact at each layer using security requirements related to confidentiality, availability, and integrity. Furthermore, this study reviews different AI-enabled solutions that can add value in preserving the security of 5G and B5G networks. Through this review analysis, we can conclude that the layered approach is quite beneficial in identifying the different threats and what security solutions can be offered to mitigate them.

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1. Introduction

1.1. General context

The 5G (Fifth Generation) networks play a vital role in mobile communication technology, ensuring high bandwidth and ultra-low latency. Initially, 5G architecture (Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Rel-15) was designed for public use, however, there was a growing interest in the deployment of 5G networks for private use as well, which was added in the second phase of the 5G networks (3GPP Rel-16 and beyond) [1,2]. Consequently, the network was categorized into two main types: public and private. The main difference between the two networks is that the public network is owned and operated for public use within a particular region. In contrast, the private network is operated for private use within a factory or organization's premises. Both types of 5G networks support cutting-edge technologies, which use different key enabling technologies. These technologies introduce new security threats and attacks to the 5G infrastructure. Despite its advantages, the 3GPP introduces security features to the 5G architecture. To support new and diverse services such as cloud-native applications, edge computing, multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO), and multi-access edge computing (MEC), there is a further increase in the attack surface for 5G applications [3]. The architecture of the 5G network provides various services, including eMBB (Enhanced Mobile Broadband), mMTC (massive Machine Type Communication), and URLLC (Ultra Reliability Low Latency Communication). With time, new applications are developing that require high data transmission rates, low latency, ultra-high throughput, multi-sense transmission, and ultra-high reliability. They are beyond the vision of 5G use cases and services [4]. The diversity of new devices and heterogeneity will be anticipated by the beyond 5G (B5G) technology, offering high data rates, low latency, high mobility, and ultra-high reliability [5].

The future wireless technology has not yet been launched. Therefore, no unified and standardized architecture has been defined for it. However, some current initiatives working on that, such as 5G-PPP (Fifth Generation Public Partnership Project) and a new program on SNS (Smart Network and Service) architecture working group (WG) [6] have been started. The 5G-PPP is in the third phase, where many of its projects were launched and are currently underway. The key challenge of 5G-PPP is to protect European leadership from new and emerging threats. In addition, the integration of Internet of Things (IoT) networks with 5G and B5G technology has transformed the traditional industry and had a profound impact on connectivity. This integration has improved the user experience and redefined the interaction with the technology. However, the 5G and B5G network infrastructure is exposed to various threats and security risks [7].

The Emergence of IoT and edge computing in 5G and B5G has significantly increased the diversity and complexity of heterogeneous networks, making them vital for various applications. The openness and diverse characteristics of heterogeneous networks make them susceptible to various security threats and privacy attacks [8]. It also inherits the security attacks from the cloud computing environment. In contrast, a decentralized architecture and a diverse deployment environment raise security concerns to a new level. The list of attacks in a heterogeneous environment includes Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks [9], malware propagation [10], and jamming attacks [11], which can affect system stability and data privacy.

Providing a comprehensive analysis of all orchestration and management challenges is beyond this paper's scope. However, the main focus of this survey is to examine different threats and attacks on private 5G and B5G networks, emphasizing the impact of security threats. Another aspect of security is to review various key enabling technologies in 5G private and B5G networks, which may be vulnerable to these threats. Threats in 5G and B5G networks encompass various aspects. The threats in 5G networks can arise from critical infrastructure and vulnerabilities in cloud computing and entry points

in network architectures. Moreover, enabling technologies such as software-defined networking, edge computing, and virtualization can be targeted by virtual machine attacks, network slicing attacks, and edge-based attacks. For the first time, ENISA [12] has discussed the threats and vulnerabilities associated with the 5G-based system. Most of the studies are related to the threats of 5G public network attacks [13, 14]. Although some studies exist that have identified the threats in 5G private networks. However, no such study that comprehensively deals with the classification and modeling of threats in 5G-private and B5G-based networks has existed. It is also essential to see the different AI/ML solutions available in the existing state-of-the-art for detecting and predicting attacks in 5G and B5G networks.

The cell structure in 5G and B5G networks represents a significant evolution in mobile communication systems, driven by enhanced performance, increased capacity, and novel applications. The cell structure is also susceptible to various attacks, including denial-of-service and unauthorized access. Moreover, 5G networks introduce new features like massive MIMO and millimeter wave technology. B5G will enhance connectivity by adding new technologies and more complex architecture. Furthermore, the architecture of the B5G network needs to support the diverse nature of devices, and their applications rely upon the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and the key technologies involved. This convergence and network heterogeneity increase the attack surface compared to the traditional mobile network, impacting the layer of the architecture and security requirements related to confidentiality, integrity, and availability. It is imperative to identify each attack distinctively and assess the impact of the attack. To the best of our knowledge, no such survey comprehensively identifies the occurrence of attacks concerning the layers of the architecture, or it is limited to specific key-enabling technologies and physical technologies. The main challenges addressed in this survey are presented below.

- 5G introduces new features like massive multiple-input-multiple output (m-MIMO) and millimeter wave (mm-Wave) technologies; these technologies introduce security threats and risks [15]. The B5G network will further enhance connectivity by adding new technologies and more complex architecture [3]. Thus, raises the attack surface in comparison to traditional wireless technologies.
- Edge computing supports 5G and B5G networks to achieve its objective by supporting eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC. Due to its utilization in key technologies including distributed architecture, NFV, and wireless networks, edge computing and edge intelligence are susceptible to various security threats and attacks [16].
- New security threats and attacks are associated with the 5G and B5G/6G applications due to their open platform, open interface, and support of various cutting-edge technologies that leverage many important key enabling technologies [17].

Inspired by the taxonomies of different threats and the evaluation of security solutions with previous-generation mobile networks, this work provides a taxonomical view of different threats occurring at the different layers of the architecture to cope with the issues mentioned earlier. Our primary focus is to review the threats to the 5G private and B5G network, classify them, and model them concerning the layers of the architecture. Datasets are vital in training the ML models for anomaly detection models in 5G and B5G networks. Using classical and newly generated datasets for 5G and B5G-based networks provides a realistic simulation environment to test the security mechanism before deployment and develop predictive security models to identify future threats. The effectiveness of anomaly detection depends on the quality and diversity of the datasets used for model training and testing. Some notable 5G and B5G network datasets include CSE-CIC-IDS2018, CIC-DoS 2019, 5G NIDD, IoT-23, CIC-DoS 2019, BoT-IoT, and UNSW-NB15. This study briefly discusses the details of these classical datasets and why new datasets are needed for 5G and B5G networks. Moreover, this study provides an analysis of open-source software used for the development

Fig. 1. Organizational structure of the survey.

and testing of 5G infrastructure. Moreover, artificial intelligence (AI) plays a vital role in detecting and mitigating attacks and preserving the privacy and security of future wireless technology. This study will also review the recent AI solutions that can aid in privacy-preserving and security solutions in 5G and B5G networks. More specifically, the review will address the following research questions:

RQ-1: What are the known threats associated with 5G private networks?

RQ-2: What are the known threats associated with the key technologies in B5G/6G networks?

RQ-3: How does AI play as a potential solution in preserving the privacy and security of 5G and B5G-based networks?

1.2. Contribution

In contrast to the traditional work on 5G and B5G technologies, this work provides a review of different threats in 5G private and B5G networks and the characterization and modeling of threats concerning the layers of the architecture. From the existing state-of-the-art, a baseline architecture is selected to model the attacks occurring at different layers of the architecture. This work adopted the generic distribution of these layers as a baseline to explain the various types of threats in 5G and B5G networks. The study has provided a list of key enabling technologies in 5G and B5G networks, along with the details of security risks to them. Moreover, an analysis of privacy-preserving AI solutions and a list of datasets adopted for detecting threats in 5G and B5G networks have been briefly presented. In light of the above, the main contribution of this survey can be summarized as follows.

1. This study provides an overview of existing research efforts to design and develop the architecture for the 5G and subsequent B5G networks.
2. We discuss the different types of cell structures in 5G and B5G networks, highlighting their advantages, disadvantages, and associated threats.
3. The study overviews key enabling technologies, open source platforms, and identifies the threats in 5G private and B5G networks/systems.
4. We adopt a 5G private network architecture based on the industrial case to characterize and model threats in the application, network, middle, and physical layers. We analyze the different types of threats, their impact, and entry points for the attacker. Moreover, an analysis of open-source software is also briefly presented.

5. We extend the layered modeling by utilizing the baseline layered architecture (6G-IoT enabled, Hexa-X E2E) to characterize and model threats into the perception, connection, and application layers, respectively. We analyze the different types of attacks, their impact, and the entry points for the attacker initiating the threats.
6. The study lists classical datasets and the need for new datasets to detect and prevent cyberattacks in 5G and B5G networks.
7. The study reviews different AI-based attacks and privacy and security solutions, through layered analysis, that can help preserve the privacy and security of 5G and B5G networks.
8. This study presents some helpful future research directions to boost the characterization and modeling of threats in 5G and B5G networks.

1.3. Scope and paper organization

This survey aims to investigate the state of the art in 5G private and B5G network architectures, cell structures, security threats, and key enabling technologies, emphasizing characterizing and modeling the threats with the layers of the architecture. This study emphasizes using Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a key enabler to provide security and privacy to future wireless technology. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the role of different surveys and this survey's position in the ongoing research activities in 5G and B5G networks. Section 3 presents an overview of threats in traditional cellular networks, the trend of industry and academia moving towards private 5G networks, and the necessity of doing security analysis in 5G private, B5G, and 6G networks are all covered in this section. In addition, the details about the different architectures and the ongoing research efforts for the 5G and B5G networks are presented in Section 4 and Section 5. This section also provides information about identifying, classifying, and modeling threats associated with the 5G and B5G networks. A list of classical datasets for detecting and identifying cyber attacks in 5G and B5G networks is provided in Section 6, along with a particular dataset created using 5G-related traffic. Section 7 discusses the role of AI as a threat vector and privacy-preserving and security solutions in 5G and B5G networks. Section 8 summarizes the paper by addressing the research questions and the limitations of this study. Finally, concluding remarks and prospective future trends are summarized in Section 9.1, 9.2 respectively. The organizational structure of this survey is illustrated in Fig. 1

2. Related work and our survey position

In 5G and B5G networks, the cell structure refers to the organization and distribution of a limited geographical area served by the base station. The 5G network is designed as a heterogeneous system, including different small cell types. The small cells have the same characteristics as base stations and are deployed in indoor and outdoor regions to provide high data rates and low latency. Different cell types include pico cells, femto cells, and micro cells [18]. The cell structure is utilized to ensure low latency, improve signal quality, and enhance the coverage and throughput of the network.

Femto cells are preferred due to their easy installation. They minimize the latency and address the issues related to cell edge coverage [19]. They are preferred in indoor applications as they enhance the system throughput and SINR (signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio). However, they are affected by the location obstacle, causing multipath propagation which reduces the SINR and coverage area [20]. Femto-cells are replaced by picocells; they are used indoors and outdoors to provide a coverage radius of up to 200 m. If it is greater than 200 m, these cells are replaced by microcells. In [21], a detailed comparison of pico, femto, and microcells was briefly presented along with their applicability in indoor and outdoor applications.

The internet-of-thing (IoT) use cases must be supported by the 5G infrastructure, and a growing number of IoT applications are expected in the future. Additionally, the adoption of new use cases will impact communication technologies [22]. The essential technologies are deployed in cells to meet the aforementioned 5G needs. In his review of 5G networks, Hani Attar et al. [15] emphasized m-MIMO and mm-Wave as the two main technologies. mm-Wave technology, which provides more bandwidth and faster data rates, and m-MIMO [23], which employs a lot of antennas at the base station to boost the capacity and effectiveness of the wireless network. The 5G network must also provide availability anywhere and anytime. It is expected that the future networks will offer huge mobility, improved connectivity, increased coverage and throughputs, and high data rates, which are not possible to achieve with poor quality signals [24].

In the context of the B5G networks, small cells, including femtocells, picocells, and microcells, play a key role in enhancing the wireless communication network [33]. These cells particularly improve the data rates and improve the capacity of the network, particularly in populated dense areas [34]. While definitions of picocells and microcells vary throughout the wireless industry, femtocells differ from small cells in that they are private, link to the network via the internet, and provide better interior coverage for smaller areas. Despite inconsistency in the terminological definitions of picocells and microcells within the wireless sector, femtocells, which are categorically different from small cells, connect to the network via the internet, are private, and provide enhanced indoor signal coverage for smaller locations. Similar to Wi-Fi hotspots, small cells are often deployed in crowded places like stadiums [35] to improve the network capacity and coverage. In [36], the study has highlighted that the limited resource utilization and reliance on backhaul connections make the small cells susceptible to DDoS attacks. DDoS attacks on small cells severely degrade the network's performance by flooding specific nodes. Another study [37] highlights the bandwidth spoofing attacks targeting the small cells on a 5G network.

Macro cell is another cell structure that provides coverage and supports higher mobility. Macro cells are essential for maintaining connectivity as the user moves between the cells, a process known as handover mobility. To handle this issue, macro cells are often deployed alongside pico cells to improve the system throughput [38]. The macro cell's high capacity and extensive coverage make it an attractive target for large-scale attacks. Macro cells can be overwhelmed by a DDoS attack, where the flood of malicious traffic targets the network infrastructure to degrade the network's performance. In [37], a study has been conducted on a macro cell infrastructure where a DDoS attack

can severely impact the performance and functionality of the network slices in 5G networks. Another study in [39] utilized a fully IP-based architecture of 5G networks that can be exploited by malicious actors to launch a DDoS attack over the internet, affecting the macro cell structure. These attacks impact the layer of the architecture and security requirements related to confidentiality, integrity, and availability. It is imperative to identify each attack distinctively, concerning the architecture layer, and assess the attack's impact.

Security and privacy are critical issues that 5G and B5G networks must address. Security and privacy issues increase as the number of users increases and data exchange increases, increasing the number of threats and security attacks [40]. The primary focus of this survey is on the two key areas: (i) security threats and attacks in 5G and B5G networks, and provide threat characterization and modeling, (ii) AI-based potential security solutions. To identify the first area, research encompasses threats in communication technologies, key-enabling technologies, application-based threats, and integration-related threats. The second important topic was how AI can stop and identify threats in 5G and B5G networks. Table 1 provides a complete overview of surveys reviewing the threats in 5G, B5G/6G based networks concerning key enabling communication, and physical technologies. Moreover, it also provides key points presented as follows:

- **Layered Threat Modeling:** Indicate whether the review paper considers the identified threats across 5G or B5G specific architectural layers (such as device layer, service layer, edge layer, application layer, and slicing layer, etc.) or component level.
- **AI methodology used:** Indicate and highlight the use of AI methodologies related to supervised/unsupervised machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), federated learning (FL), etc., in the surveyed work.
- **Depth of security evaluation:** Quantitatively describe how the paper analyzes threat, threat impact, defense mechanism, and other integration-related issues by categorizing them as low, moderate, and high.

Moreover, Table 1 provides a quick overview of the recent work concerning the privacy and security of 5G and B5G networks. We have provided a brief description of the threats associated with the integration of AI/ML, IoT, IT (Information Technology), OT (Operational Technology), and IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things) with the 5G and B5G-based system.

The article [25] examines the occurrence of different attacks in 5G and B5G networks, emphasizing the layer of the architecture and the consequences of an attack. In [27], the authors reviewed the security and privacy issues of B5G/6G networks in the physical, connection, and service layers. The aforementioned study also identifies new threat vectors and security issues in distributed environment settings. Moreover, integrating pervasive intelligence (AI/ML) with future wireless technology is also considered a threat to the B5G and 6G networks. The first analysis of security and privacy issues in B5G is presented in [41]. The study has highlighted the importance of physical layer protection, deep slicing networks, quantum computing, AI security, novel data protection mechanisms like differential privacy, distributed ledger technology, and the use of AI to mitigate and protect personal data in B5G networks. The study also elaborated on the B5G threats and possible solutions concerning the layer of architecture including the physical layer, connection layer, and application layer.

Different surveys [28,29] have been conducted, focused on identifying the AI/ML and integration-based threats. Moreover, integrating IT, OT, IoT, and IIT with the B5G network poses different security threats and cyber risks, as reviewed in [31,32,42]. The list of attacks is as follows, (1) Network slice theft & misconfiguration, (2) Adversarial attack on DL process, (3) Unauthorized access to SDN controller, (4) MITM, (5) Insider threat, (6) Side channel attack, (7) Malware,

Table 1
Comparison of existing related surveys.

Ref	Year	Paper	Mobile	Threats in 5G and B5G				Layered threat modeling	AI methodology used	Depth of security evaluation	Key contribution
				Threat taxonomy	Layer identification	Threat impact	Integration related threats				
[14]	2022	review	5G Public Networks	✓	✓	✓	X	✓ (Architectural layers + component level)	X	N/A	The study has focused on the modeling of threats and adversary groups in 5G-based public networks
[25]	2021	Survey	B5G, 6G	X	✓	✓	✓	✓ (Architectural layers)	✓ (ML, DL, FL)	Moderate	The study has focused on the identification of threats and security flaws along with providing potential solutions
[26]	2022	Survey	5G Private Networks	✓	X	✓	X	✓ (Component level)	✓ (ML, DL, RL)	Low	The study discusses the different security issues in 5G private network
[27]	2022	Survey	B5G, 6G	✓	X	X	✓	✓ (Architectural layer)	✓ (DL, FL)	Moderate (Particular privacy-related)	The study has discussed the different privacy perspectives in B5G/6G networks
[28]	2020	Survey	B5G, 6G	✓	X	✓	✓	X	✓ (ML, DL, NN)	High	The survey discusses the ML-based privacy attack and link privacy issues with the type of attack
[29]	2024	Survey	B5G, 6G	✓	X	✓	✓	✓	✓ (ML, DL)	High	The survey focused on the AI-based threats in B5G/6G networks
[30]	2023	review	B5G, 6G	✓	X	✓	X	X	X	Moderate	The study has focused on the taxonomy of threats in B5G/6G communication using the CIA
[31,32]	2019, 2021	Survey	B5G, 6G	X	✓	X	✓	X	✓ (ML, DL,FL)	Low	The study focuses on the threats associated with the integration of IT, OT, and IIT with the B5G/6G networks
Our survey	2024	Survey	Private 5G, B5G network	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ (Architectural layers)	✓ (ML, DL, FL, LLMs)	High	Our study has focused on 5G private threats and B5G, and AI-enabled security solutions

(8) IP/MAC spoofing, (9) User identity theft, (10) Malicious payload injection, (11) DoS/DDoS, (12) Zero-day, (13) Session hijacking, (14) Network/ host intrusion, (15) Sensor spoofing, (16) IMSI catching, (17) Phishing, (18) botnet, (19) Ransomware, (20) False data injection, (21) social Engineering, (22) Brute force and (23) Eavesdropping.

The aforementioned research fails to define the specific details of an attack, which layer is affected by the occurrence of the attack, the impact of the attack, and the component being affected. A review has been conducted to identify threats in 5G public networks using a layered approach [14]. In a recent survey [26], authors highlighted the threats and security issues in 5G private networks. However, the study neither classifies nor models the various threats to the layers of the architecture nor provides any information about the entry points for the attacker. Another similar study identifies the different threats in B5G/6G communication [30]. The study classified the attacks using these five categories (confidentiality, availability, integrity, authentication, and access control parameters) and helped to understand and mitigate the security risks in communication systems.

However, none of the single surveys has discussed comprehensively the characterization of threats in 5G private networks and B5G/6G networks. It is imperative to have a holistic view of the threat modeling approach that can incorporate the future wireless technology threats distinctly at different layers of the architecture while considering the respective technologies and components involved in each architecture layer. The layered approach for the architecture will be beneficial for the operator and developers to identify the specific attack on each layer, along with the fundamental protocols or technologies that impact the B5G application. A detailed discussion on the privacy issues in B5G and 6G networks is presented in [27]. However, limited attention is paid to the cyber threats and security challenges in 5G private and B5G networks. In this survey, we are more concerned with the information security threats in 5G and B5G networks, along with reviewing the different security and privacy mechanisms linked with using AI to mitigate cyber-attacks.

3. Overview of the threats

In this section, we provide an overview of threats associated with the generation of mobile networks from 1G to 5 G. The 5G network is involved in various key technologies. The threats associated with the key technologies involved are also briefly presented. In the next section, we provide the role of 5G public, private, and B5G networks in industry. More specifically, why is there a need for a security analysis of the 5G private and beyond networks?

3.1. Previous generation threats

The evolution of mobile networks has faced many challenges, focusing on security considerations. In the first generation (1G) to transfer the data, an analog modulation technique was used, which has two main dominant issues: the handover problem and a lack of security consideration. In the second generation (2G), network security is improved by authentication and encryption; however, this generation still has many vulnerabilities associated with one-way authentication and encryption. In 2000, the 3G was launched, covering up the previous generation's authentication issue using two-way authentication, increasing transmission speed, and internet access. Moreover, 3G also includes authentication and key agreement (AKA) and 3GPP (Third Generation Partnership Project), which allows complete access to control security system, air interface security, and user authentication. Although the 3GPP has developed security protocols, vulnerabilities still exist related to the registration of mobile devices, base stations, and wireless access, including data leakage, Denial-of-service (DoS), and downgrade attacks [43]. Despite the advancement of 3G, there are privacy concerns and IP vulnerabilities. The 4G architecture is based on IPs and utilizes cryptographic algorithms and protocols to secure communications. However, the media access control layer (MAC) of the 4G architecture is vulnerable to various attacks and struggles to

Table 2
Threads associated with the previous generation.

Generation	Architecture feature	Attacks	Attack impact
3G security	Five essential features are included, Security for user domains, network domains, network access, applications, and visibility of security configuration.	Eavesdropping, Impersonate attacks, Man-in-the-middle attacks (MITM), spoofing, and location exposure [43]	Compromising integrity, unauthorized access to the data and services, and other AKA sniffing attacks [43]
4G security	4G architecture based on IP, uses different sets of new cryptographic algorithms, cryptographic graphic protocols, and integrity algorithms.	Theft of Service, DoS, User ID theft, IP Address spoofing, and intrusion attacks, APT and DDoS affect the security of the system [44].	Compromise integrity, Unauthorized access to the data, Authentication issues
	MAC(media access control) layer security	Attacks are related to the execution of wireless application DoS, eavesdropping, replay attack, and malware application attacks [44]	Compromising the integrity of the data [44]
5G security	It consists of three main components such as old thread, heterogeneous connected devices Softwarization, virtualization, and network slicing	Most of the attacks target the SDN controller and cloud SDN threats involve centralizing network flow (a DoS attack), exposing API to unwanted software, and launching open flow [45] Potential attacks on network slicing are DoS, theft of information via compromised slices, resource depletion, injection, and impersonate based attacks [46]	Unavailability of services, compromising integrity, confidentiality violation

efficiently manage the large number of connected devices, leading to a degradation of the performance and reliability of the network [44]. Moreover, the MAC layer lacks the flexibility to support emerging technologies such as network slicing, edge computing, and dynamic spectrum allocation. Detailed information on threats associated with the previous generation and concerns and their respective impact is presented in Table 2.

5G networks enable numerous cutting-edge technologies that utilize critical supporting technologies such as Network Function Virtualization (NFV), Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), and Network Slicing (NC). Despite having the benefits of these aforementioned technologies they are susceptible to various cyberthreats. For example, the centralized control plane of SDN makes it susceptible to DoS and injection attacks, among other types of attacks, which compromises the system's integrity [45]. Hypervisors are the key components in NFV environment. Exploiting the vulnerabilities in hypervisors leads to different security attacks, including unauthorized access to other virtual machines (VMs), Man-in-the-Middle, and other application programming interface (API) attacks. Moreover, in a 5G-based system, the operator orchestrates and manages the network, tailored to the demands of applications within the 5G core network of the 3GPP 5G system. Potential attacks on network slicing are Denial-of-service (DoS), information theft via the compromised slices, and resource depletion attacks. Other types of attacks associated with network slicing include traffic injection and impersonation-based attacks [46]. These attacks are mostly related to the increase of threat surface and inadequate isolation among the slices at different levels [47]

3.2. 5G public, private, and beyond 5G networks

In contrast to public networks, private networks are typically owned and operated by the industry and academic institutions. Due to digitization, industries increasingly rely on public cloud storage to store data and streamline business processes [48]. However, a couple of issues make it challenging for the industry and academia to share their

workload and data on the public cloud and follow their strict guidelines and policies. Security is one of the major issues among them. Other issues include the strict latency requirements to process the data and the difficulties while making the connection remotely.

In a world where data breaches and cyber-attacks are common, industries must use their customized security policies and local storage for their data and workload, which is impossible with the traditional 5G public networks. Due to this shortcoming, 5G private networks are gaining more attention. Moreover, productivity and safety can be improved with a 5G private network without needing a mobile network operator [49]. A couple of research efforts have been made in defining the B5G network architecture; some current initiatives, including HEXA-X and 5G-PPP, already exist in the literature about their design, development, and architecture. It is expected that future wireless technology will adopt several concepts from the previous generation, including enabling technologies and providing services to the diverse use cases while supporting cross-domain integration [50]. At the same time, it increases the attack surface compared to traditional technologies. concluding that 5G and B5G infrastructure is exposed to various threats and security risks.

Most of the studies in existing state-of-the-art are related to the threats on 5G public networks [13]. For example, ENISA [12] has discussed the characterization of threats and vulnerabilities associated with the 5G-based system. The high-level classification of attacks includes eavesdropping, accidents, failure/malfunions, disasters, outages, and legal, physical, and abuse of asset-related attacks. In [51], the authors have established a three-dimensional threat taxonomy for identifying NFV threats in a 5G-based system. In the existing state-of-the-art, most of the studies are related to the threats of 5G public network attacks [13]. Another study mentioned in [14] has classified the different threats and modeled them in various layers of the architecture. The modeling approach also provided us with information on the threat, entry points, the impact of the attack, and what components are being affected in each layer. Although some studies highlight the security issues in 5G-based private networks [48,52]. The study in [48]

discussed the private 5G networks in the context of security policies and mechanisms to secure communication. In [52], the author has discussed the 3GPP architecture and the security issues with 5G private networks. Moreover, a report [53], discussed the different types of attacks has been presented that could occur on private 5G networks.

In the realm of B5G networks, a couple of studies has been conducted that identify the different attacks in B5G applications using various communication technologies [54]. For instance, multi-sensory XR applications involving the use of molecular communication, terahertz (THz) communication, and quantum communication (QC) technology are susceptible to different attacks, including access control attacks, malicious behavior, and exposure of data transmission. Another B5G application, connected robotics and autonomous systems (CRAS), is involved in the key technology of AI and visible light communication (VLC). The most problematic attacks on CRAS are related to data transmission, encryption, and malicious behavior. A partial contribution is made in [25] by identifying the attacks corresponding to the layer of the architecture and the consequences of the particular attack in 5G and B5G infrastructure. Moreover, the study provided the first analysis of the privacy and security challenges associated with future wireless technology. Although the studies mentioned above do provide threat analysis in 5G and B5G networks, they are either focused on 5G public network threats or privacy and security issues concerning the B5G networks.

To the best of our knowledge, there is no such study existing in the existing literature that focuses on the classification and modeling of threats in 5G-based private networks. As highlighted previously, the architecture of the B5G network needs to support the diverse nature of devices, and its applications rely upon the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and the key technologies involved. This convergence and network heterogeneity increase the attack surface as compared to the traditional mobile network. These attacks have an impact on the layer of the architecture and security requirements related to confidentiality, integrity, and availability. It is imperative to identify each attack distinctively and assess the impact of the attack. In other words, there is no such survey that comprehensively identifies the occurrence of attacks concerning the layers of the architecture, or it is limited to specific key-enabling technologies and communication technologies.

4. Private 5G layered architecture & enabling technologies

In this section, we list some open-source initiatives and research efforts for creating a 5G private network. These initiatives include open-source RAN targeting the user equipment (UE) and open-source core. Additionally, we presented the details of different architectures proposed for the 5G private networks and the key enablers that make them possible, along with the details of security threats and attacks associated with them. Finally, we have provided the characterization and modeling of threats using a layered architecture.

4.1. Private 5G layered architecture

According to the 3GPP specification, two basic architectures were proposed for the 5G private network, namely (i) standalone (SA) and (ii) Public network integrated. The 5G SA architecture is comprised of 5G New Radio (NR) and 5G core network (5GC). It supports the different services and use cases in 5G networks. The second type of architecture is built with a private network deployment done with the support of public networks. This deployment has lower customization, self-control, and security [48]. The use case of private networks includes industry 4.0, video streaming, healthcare, AR/VR and smart grid adopted from [55].

Different open-source software has been offered for building core and RAN solutions for 5G and B5G-based networks. The srsRAN (also known as SRS LTE) [56], OpenAirInterface (OAI) [57], and UERANSIM (UE and RAN simulator) [58] are open-source RAN software

solutions used for the development, experiment, and deployment of 4G LTE and 5G NR mobile communication networks. These solutions provide support for 5G standalone (SA) and non-standalone (NSA) modes for the development process, to enable the interaction of UE with gNB without needing physical hardware. The srsRAN and UERANSIM can simulate and emulate essential 5G components such as UE and RAN, but their real-world implementation is limited because of integration challenges with existing infrastructure and compliance with regulatory standards. srsRAN works only with single-input-single-output (SISO), whereas, OAI supports single-input-single-output (SISO) and MIMO and offers better throughput under the same signal-to-noise-plus-interference (SNIR) conditions. Moreover, in contrast to their performance, srsRAN performs better in uplink and OAI performs better in downlink tasks.

In short, srsRAN, OpenAirInterface (OAI), and UERANSIM [59] are open-source RAN software solutions used for the development, experimentation, and deployment of 4G LTE and 5G NR mobile communication networks. These open-source RAN solutions are extensively used in academia and research due to their accessibility and adherence to standard protocols. srsRAN and UERANSIM can simulate and emulate essential 5G components such as UE and RAN, but their real-world implementation is limited due to integration challenges with existing infrastructure and compliance with regulatory standards.

Open5GS, OpenAI5GC, OpenAI5GS, and Free5GCore (5GC) [59] are prominent open-source software solutions developed to support 5G core network functionalities in line with 3GPP specifications. In [60], the study highlights that these 5G core platforms provide transparency for auditing and verification purposes. Real-world applications require strong capabilities and features not entirely developed in the aforementioned platforms. For instance, these tools follow the 3GPP specifications; they may not support the latest features and optimizations, such as Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF), which is crucial for network automation and management. Moreover, the performance indicator can also significantly vary in these platforms. For example, Open5GS provides better latency support for the control plane procedures, whereas OAI outperforms in data throughput, and Free5GS has the lowest power consumption and can contribute significantly to specific applications. So organizations need to make a tradeoff to choose the right platform depending on their needs. Furthermore, there is a notable gap between the Free5GS and OpenAI deployment options, as the complexity of installation and configuration is relatively easier for Free5GS compared to OpenAI due to the lower accessibility to the documentation. M. Amini et al. [61] highlighted in their study that one of the significant security concerns with OAI 5G RAN is the interoperability and interaction with various 5G core network software. P. Linh et al. have highlighted in their research [59] that Open AI and free5GC both rely on Docker-compose files using single host deployment. If one container is compromised, the attacker gains access to the entire host or interferes with the other containers. This single-host deployment has also led to scalability issues and a lack of redundancy in distributed multi-node setups. Therefore, single-node deployments cannot be applied in a multi-node or cloud environment.

The open nature of aforementioned platforms often allows for broader community auditing and transparency, which can enhance security through collaborative scrutiny. Most of the open-source 5G core and RAN offer a valuable platform in building testbeds for research, testing, and prototype purposes, and are not always deployed directly in commercial and production-grade systems. In summary, transitioning these open-source platforms from a testbed environment to a fully operational 5G environment requires extensive testing and validation, representing a resource-intensive task that these platforms may not adequately address.

The main concept behind using a private architecture is to fulfill the need for a specific application. The idea of a private 5G network for industrial communication is based on network slice eMBB, mMTC, and URLLC applications. Network slicing is the key enabling technology

Fig. 2. 5G private architecture based on industry [64].

used for the deployment of public networks integrated with private networks. Each slice is built to fulfill the specific network capability and characteristics of a particular use case. The slicing architecture [62] consists of 3 layers: the physical layer, the network slice instance layer, and the application layer, respectively. In which the network slicing layer is responsible for the creation of multiple virtual networks on a single physical infrastructure. Each slice supports specific application requirements [63]. For example, eMBB supports applications related to AR/VR and video streaming to support high bandwidth, mMTC supports many devices requiring high bandwidth and special services associated with MIMO, and URLLC is used to support autonomous vehicles and remote surgery. Slicing seems crucial for autonomous vehicles and remote surveys; these types of applications are deployed with the help of edge computing capabilities. Slicing architecture can be applied to intelligent transportation, smart homes, smart grids, and Industry 4.0. The slicing architecture [62] consists of 3 layers: the physical layer, the network slice instance layer, and the application layer, respectively. Each slice is constructed to satisfy a particular use case's unique network capabilities and characteristics. Network slicing is the key enabling technology in 5G private networks, which deploys public networks integrated with the private network.

To support the vertical industry or industry 4.0, the edge computing architecture [65] has been proposed. It consists of three layers: device layer, edge layer, and cloud application layer. More importantly, the edge layer provides time-sensitive services, and the cloud application layer obtains and processes massive data from the edge layer to make non-real-time decisions. The edge layer utilizes SDN and NFV; threats related to the enabling technologies also apply to the edge layer. The edge layer is susceptible to DoS, side-channel, and VM-based attacks.

To address the RQ-1, we have looked into the existing literature to identify the known threats in 5G private networks, considering the layered approach of the architecture. The layered approach helps to identify the different threats impacting the 5G-based application. The range of these threats is from RAN to core risks, air interface attacks, Application program interface (API) exposure attacks, 5G core and automation, passive attacks, and connected devices attacks. To demonstrate these threats, we have adopted a private 5G network architecture [64] based on an industrial case of video streaming as shown in Fig. 2. The private network architecture consists of four layers, including the perception layer, network layer, middle layer, and application layer. The details of each layer are presented below.

- **Perception layer:** This layer is responsible for managing and controlling end user devices, providing connectivity and communication to private networks. The devices can range from mobile phones, drones, IoT devices, sensor data, and autonomous vehicles to network access points.
- **Middle Layer:** It is responsible for providing the application data interface for the exchange of services in accordance with the Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) model. This layer acts as a hub for collecting and analyzing the data collected from the perception layer. The layer also uses some AI-based analytics to get valuable insights from the data.
- **Network Layer:** It is responsible for communicating between different system components. It utilizes a private 5G network to ensure high data rates and seamless connectivity for real-time data sharing with users and devices.
- **The application layer:** It is responsible for providing various applications and services to the user. The services related to the 5G private network include augmented reality, smart grid, smart healthcare, video streaming, smart transportation, and others. It also provides content to the user in an interactive manner.

4.2. Threat vector and dimension

In this section, we explicitly clarified the structure and foundation of the threat classification as shown in Fig. 3. The term taxonomy in our work refers to a structured and hierarchical classification of 5G private-related threats based on the impact of the attack. To characterize threats, a 5G private architecture is selected as a baseline based on an industrial video streaming case and models threats using the perception, middle, network, and application layers, respectively. This approach was adopted from the layered methodology presented by Farooqui et al. [14], who proposed a layered-based threat model for 5G systems, where threats are grouped under unique categorization by the architectural layer and technological domains. Different threats concerning the layers of the 5G private network architecture are presented below.

- The perception layer encompasses the threats related to communication technologies, key enabling technologies, basestations, and devices, sensor data-related threats, and security attacks. The attack surface for the devices is extremely volatile, and most of the attacks associated with this layer are malware, botnets, DOS/DDoS, and spoofing attacks.
- The middle layer involves AI-related tasks. The security threats and risks are involved with the use of AI/ML, which include data manipulation, data exfiltration, and injection-based attacks, where the attacker can alter the processed data, compromising the overall confidentiality and integrity of the system.
- The network layer provides the connectivity to the core network function, and components to the basestation. Several threats and security risks associated with the core network functions are identified in [66]. Both the user and the control plane are affected by these attacks, which include DoS and spoofing attacks on Access and Mobility Management function (AMF) as well as User Plane Function (UPF).
- The application layer provides services and an application interface to the users. The services are provided through an Application programmable Interface (API), and the threat faced by the services has an overlap with the modern internet-based applications. This layer encompasses security attacks such as unauthorized access and exploitation of application vulnerabilities. Attackers might try to take over streaming services or augmented reality features, disrupting the services and unauthorized content distribution.

Fig. 3. Threat vector for 5G private networks.

Fig. 4. Key enablers of 5G private networks.

4.3. Enabling technologies

In this section, we have provided a list of key-enabling technologies that are possible with the private 5G network, including URLLC, private edge computing, Device-to-Device (D2D) communication, and network slicing. The overview of the key technology is presented in Fig. 4. Communication technologies such as MIMO and mm-Wave are also presented, along with information on threats and security attacks, and the communication technologies. The details of these threats are presented below.

- **URLLC**: This is a key enabling technology in 5G private networks. URLLC utilizes short transmission intervals, spatial diversity, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) base station densification, and Device-to-device (D2D) communication collectively to improve value, reliability, reduce latency, and increase the efficiency of 5G private networks. The most common attack on the URLLC is the DoS attack, which can disrupt the low-latency requirements, affecting the critical application [48].
- **Private Edge Computing**: An essential enabling technology for 5G private networks that are pushing data-intensive tasks towards the edge. It offers several advantages such as location awareness, real-time response, high mobility support, low bandwidth requirements, high throughput, and low latency. It also offers customized services for local demands and network configurations. Moreover, it offers an open radio network platform to facilitate storage as well as processing capabilities. Through the application programming interface (API), private edge computing facilitates distributed AI and cloud computing in 5G-based private networks [67]. The extension of cloud and its services to the edge of the cloud, also known as mobile edge computing (MEC). Therefore, MEC has a wide range of applications such as healthcare, connected vehicles, video analytics, virtual or augmented reality, smart communities, mobile big data analytics, and smart grid [68].
- **Network Slicing**: Network slicing plays a critical role in 5G private networks due to the varying quality of service (QoS) to support the diverse use cases. Time-Division-Multi-Access (TDMA) is used to allocate resources and to prevent interference. Due to virtual isolation instead of physical isolation in the slicing, side-channel attacks are the most prevalent threats in slicing 5G private networks [69]. This virtual isolation often includes logical and temporal separation. Network slicing, a developing technology with several key benefits for the deployment of 5G private networks, has still raised a number of research issues for the business and networking sector.
- **Interference Management**: In the use of public and private networks in 5G private networks, interference can occur from multiple signal transmissions. This interference leads to a negative impact on the latency and the reliability of the network. Management of interference is linked to attacks, such as unauthorized attacks, leading to misdirection and data breaches. Moreover, sending a harmful signal to the device, causing rapid battery depletion, these attacks cause serious issues in mission-critical applications and IIoT devices [70].
- **Localization and tracking**: Many 5G applications, such as autonomous vehicles or robots, rely on accurate positioning systems. Radio frequency (RF) based localization is critical in 5G private networks. The 5G new radio (NR) uses multiple antennas to make accurate positioning possible. Despite having the advantages of private networks, the attacker can exploit vulnerabilities to the localized system via spoofing and side-channel attacks, to deduce the device's location [71].
- **Massive multiple input multiple output (m-MIMO)**: The m-MIMO technology supports a large number of antennas compared to 4G, which utilizes 4–8 antennas. Despite having the advantages, they are also associated with different security attacks and risks; among them, the signaling threat is the most common in m-MIMO technology. Moreover, using AI with the m-MIMO technology introduces adversarial attacks that exploit the vulnerabilities in the AI models, resulting in performance issues and impacting the integrity of the 5G network [72].
- **Millimeter Wave (mm-Wave)**: Frequency bands signal in mm-wave technology can travel only over short distances, resulting in smaller coverage capacity than conventional frequency bands. The technology also suffers from signal attenuation and poor diffraction caused by channel conditions and path losses that ultimately deteriorate the signal quality. The poor diffraction makes it vulnerable to blocking an obstacle under line-of-sight (LoS) transmission. To overcome the challenges of mm-Wave, the study in [73] proposes to deploy the mm-Wave with the integration of small cell, MIMO, and beamforming to improve latency, coverage, and capacity.
- **Beamforming**: This is another key technology that allows the radio wave to travel in a particular direction. The focus of radio wave transmission increases spectral efficiency and reduces interference while maintaining the simultaneous delivery of data from multiple antennas, leading to an increased data rate [74]. The effectiveness of beamforming is often hindered by the challenges encountered in acquiring the channel state information (CSI), which leads the adversary to intercept or eavesdrop on the communication. This results in compromising the integrity and reliability of the network operations.

- **Device-to-Device Communication (D2D):** Rather than following the uplink and downlink topological structure, D2D communication enables the physically close devices to directly communicate using the sidelink. D2D communication experiences shorter link distances and fewer hops compared to uplink and downlink communication. In this way, low latency, and high reliability are particularly relevant with the new enhancement in 5G NR V2X domains. Despite the advantages of D2D communication, including a direct link with the device, an attacker can still intercept sensitive information being shared between them. Additionally, D2D communication suffers from interference from cellular users and other D2D users, which can degrade the quality of the communication. Moreover, as the user moves, the network must adapt to the changes to secure the connection, which can lead to many vulnerabilities during the transaction [75].
- **Small Cell Deployment:** Applying small cells in a 5G network can benefit the network in a number of ways: (i) they have the potential to facilitate the connectivity of numerous devices such as mMTC, which would otherwise put some additional load on macro cells, (ii) they can improve the signal quality for the UE and reduce the latency for URLLC communication and (iii) by increasing the power of small cells, the overall throughput of the network can be enhanced, and addressing the need of user equipment's (UE) for high-rate data transmission. Moreover, small cells are linked with challenges such as power demands, coverage radius, deployment and testing, and mobility and handover issues.

A. Categorization of security threats: The first step here is to classify the identified threats under a single category to present the different threats on a baseline 5G private architecture. These threats are related to communication and key enabling technologies in 5G private networks. Fig. 5 (<https://bit.ly/44ZgAbf> accessed on 26 July 2025) classifies the threats into various categories, whereas Fig. 6 (<https://bit.ly/3J38WU1> accessed on 26 July 2025), maps the threats with the layers of the architecture. Below, we have described each threat under a single category.

- **RAN Threats:** In a 5G private network, RAN provides authentication, session management, user credentials, etc., to connect the devices and UE to the basestation. The most common attacks are the DoS and MITM attacks, disrupting device communication, compromising the integrity and confidentiality of the information [76].
- **Beamforming-based threats:** In 5G private networks, two key technologies are included (m-MIMO and mm-wave). Both technologies support high-frequency RAN solutions and are considered a significant threat to 5G private networks. The attacks associated with the m-MIMO technology include jamming, eavesdropping, and contamination attacks while estimating channel state information. One such attack on m-MIMO is a pilot contamination attack (PCA), in a 5G private network, which involves attackers sending identical pilot sequences as legitimate users, resulting in disrupting the active user detection and channel estimation [77]. Other key technology associated with beamforming, named as mm-Wave, attacks associated with the mm-Wave include jamming attacks, eavesdropping, and pilot spoofing attacks [78] due to unsecured wireless communication.
- **Edge computing attacks:** The most common attacks on edge computing include DDoS, jamming, and malware propagation attacks. API vulnerability in 5G private networks is linked with various security threats and attacks, including data exposure, Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks, authentication hijacking, and injection attacks. In contrast to conventional centralized cloud computing, the private edge is installed in a distributed manner that can reduce the possibility that a signal point failure in a network or a cyber attack could destroy the whole network. In this way, private

edge computing plays a key role in protecting the local area and other sensitive data from digital attacks [79]. Edge computing is a significant concern affecting the performance of the system and user trust [80].

- **Network slicing attacks:** Network slicing is a key technology in 5G private networks. Due to the virtual slice, various threats are included in 5G network slicing, such as misconfiguration of the slice, side channel, slice isolation bypass, or other spoofing-related attacks between different slices [69].
- **Malicious code/software:** 5G private network introduces security challenges regarding malicious code and software, primarily due to the increased complexity and inter-connectivity of these networks. Malicious code and software introduce vulnerability by using malware, spyware, viruses, trojans, and botnets, potentially disrupting the services and compromising sensitive data, impacting both the users and the organizations [81].
- **Network configuration manipulation:** In a 5G private network, misconfiguration of functions and services redirects legitimate traffic users and network functions to the malicious endpoints. In [82], the study has discussed the vulnerabilities exploiting the misconfigured services and functions, particularly targeting private 5G campus networks. These vulnerabilities can lead to unauthorized access, data breaches, and disruption of services/functions.
- **Signaling Threat:** Signaling storm or threat is a significant concern in 5G-based private networks. In [83], the authors have presented an attack scenario in which a signaling threat is identified due to the 5G air interface vulnerabilities during authentication. Data was collected from the N2 target base station to perform this attack, and 50 UEs were utilized for the experimentation. The collected data come from 2000 groups involved in the authentication process. Another study in [84] identifies the DDoS signaling attack targeting the 5G Core network functions.
- **Spoofing attack:** Spoofing, or more specifically, DNS spoofing [26, 53], is a significant concern in 5G private networks in which the attacker gains access to the network via IMSI (international mobile subscriber identity) impersonation and can launch the spoofing attack. In 5G NR, the attacker exploits the vulnerabilities of the 5G primary synchronization signals (PSS) by transmitting fake signals to the UE to confuse the user about the legitimacy of a cell. In this way, UE is connected to the rough base station, potentially allowing the attacker to control the UE communication (intercept, manipulate, or block the data) [85].
- **Jamming/Denial-of-service:** Denial-of-service or Distributed Denial-of-service [26,53] is one of the most notorious and damaging attacks in a 5G private network that can be performed using the compromised device. This type of jamming attack mostly occurs at the physical layer involving the 5G RAN and 5G NR modules. For example, in 5G NR, the network utilizes orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), making it susceptible to selective jamming attacks. To perform this attack, the attacker exploits the predictable time-frequency structure of OFDM to jam the specific subcarriers used by the physical broadcast channel (PBCH). Thus, the target is on the PBCH, which is used to transmit the essential information, such as the master information block (MIBs). By jamming PBCH the attacker prevents the UE from accessing the network [86].
- **Unauthorized access:** The attack happens when the attacker gets between the user and the server and sniffs the data. The attacker captures the data and inserts the new data. MITM attacks also involve unauthorized access to private networks by sending harmful signals that drain the device battery rapidly. This type of attack has serious consequences for those networks with mission-critical IoT and IIoT devices [48].
- **Timing attack:** Also known as a power consumption attack, they are considered a significant threat to the private 5G deployment, particularly in the context of edge computing, and IoT.

Fig. 5. Taxonomy of 5G Private threat categorization.

The main aim of the attack is to drain the energy resources of the user devices, edge nodes, or basestations, leading to device availability and potential failure of the devices. The most common attacks include the energy depletion attack (EDA) and synergistic power attack (SPA). EDA mainly targets the IoT devices, which ultimately leads to reducing the battery lifespan, whereas SPA focuses on the power outage issue in data centers with a focus on causing power outages in data centers [87]

- **Tampering attack:** In this attack, the attacker intercepts the valid data and maliciously replies. The attacker may inject false data or fabricated content with emphasis on the protocol level and configuration threats in non-public or private deployments. One

such attack is the UPF tampering, in which the attacker can send a malicious PFCP session modification request to the user plane function (UPF), to drop user packets and redirect the legitimate traffic to the malicious end-points, directly impacting the data integrity and availability. An attacker can also perform a MITM tampering attack on a 5G private network on a user's slice request before it reaches the slice management function, leading to unauthorized slice allocation or incorrect configuration [88].

- **Eavesdropping:** In this type of attack, the attacker hijacks the transmission channel and intercepts the network's content without a legitimate request. The attacker can also attempt to consume

Table 3

Categorization of 5G private threats mapped with layers.

Attack category	Attack types	Impact	Entry points	Affected layers	Services involved	Use cases involved
RAN Threats [76]	Jamming, DoS Compromise UE, rough Basestation, sniffing attack	Unavailability of services, integrity violation Confidentiality violation	Open RAN interfaces, wireless interfaces	Network layer, Middle layer, Application layer	eMBB, URLLC, mMTC	Smart cities, connected vehicle, industrial automation
Beamforming-based attack [77,78]	Jamming, Eavesdropping, Contamination attack, pilot spoofing attack	Unavailability of services,	Antenna arrays, channel state feedback	Network layer, Middle layer, Application layer	eMBB, URLLC, mMTC	Connected vehicles, smart manufacturing, Augmented reality/virtual reality (AR/VR)
Edge computing attack [79]	DDoS, Jamming Malware propagation	Unavailability of services, integrity violation	MEC server core functions	Network layer, Middle layer	URLLC, mMTC	Healthcare, virtual reality video streaming/analytics, smart communi- ties/campuses, Smart grid,
Network Slicing attack [69]	Slice isolation bypass Slice channel attack slice spoofing	Unavailability of services, integrity violation Confidentiality violation	Network slice orchestrator, slice manager, shared virtualized infrastructure	Network layer, Middle layer, Application layer	eMBB, URLLC, mMTC	Industry 4.0, autonomous vehicles, smart manufacturing, Augmented reality/virtual reality(AR/VR)
Malicious software [26,53]	Ransomware, botnet, malware, Viruses Spyware attacks	Unavailability of services, integrity violation	MEC server core functions	Network layer, perception layer	eMBB, mMTC	Smart grid Industry 4.0 Campus
Network Configuration manipulation [82]	Routing table manipulation, registration of Malicious functions, DNS manipulation, Exploitation of misconfigured data	Unavailability of services, integrity violation	SDN controller, Network functions, DNS server	Middle layer, Network layer	eMBB, mMTC	Smart grid Industry 4.0 Smart Campus
Signaling threats [26,53]	Signaling storms, Signaling threats	Unavailability of services, integrity violation	MEC server core functions	Network layer, perception layer	eMBB, mMTC	Smart grid Industry 4.0 Campus
Spoofing Attack [26,53]	Location spoofing, DNS spoofing, DNS reflection- amplification, ransomware, botnet, malicious attacks	Unavailability of services, resource exhaustion	Misconfigured server, MEC server, AMF, SMF, DNS server/protocol	Network layer, perception layer	eMBB, mMTC	Smart grid Industry 4.0 Smart Campus
DoS [26,53]	DDoS, flooding, jamming, network overloading, network interface overload	Authentication failure, unavailability	Server, virtual functions, AMF (Access & Mobility Function), SMF (Session Management Function)	Network layer, middle layer	eMBB, URLLC	Video streaming Connected vehicle Healthcare Smart Campuses
Unauthorized Access [26,48]	Man-in-the-middle (MITM), IMSI impersonation	Compromising confidentiality, integrity, availability	Weak authentication mechanism	Network layer, perception layer, middlelayer	URLLC, mMTC	IoT systems, Healthcare Smart manufacturing
Timing attack [26,48]	Power consumption attack battery drain	Compromising confidentiality, integrity, availability	Basestation edge node, user devices	Network layer, perception layer, middlelayer	URLLC, mMTC	IoT systems, edge computing system
Tampering [26]	UPF tampering, Configuration tampering, Slice tampering replay attacks	Compromising data integrity and confidentiality, delays leading to unavailability	Base stations, wireless communication links, network servers, databases	Network layer, Perception layer, and middle layer	eMBB, URLLC	Industry 4.0, video streaming, Augmented Reality/Virtual, Reality (AR/VR)
Eavesdropping [26]	Session hijacking, device/data interception	Integrity and confidentiality violation	Virtual machine, SMF, network functions	Network layer, middle layer	eMBB, URLLC	Manufacturing Video streaming
Manipulation of Hardware/Software [26]	Side channel attack, rogue base station	Unavailability, integrity compromise, system destruction	Virtual machine, user devices, network functions	Network layer, middle layer perception layer	URLLC, mMTC	Smart grid, Smart manufacturing Smart Campus healthcare
Impersonate attack [26,53]	Uplink/downlink impersonation	Authentication failure, integrity and non-repudiation issues	Insecure implementation of operator, 3GPP protocol flaws	Perception layer, middle layer	URLLC, mMTC	Smart monitoring, Healthcare, Smart manufacturing

the controller to shut down the network or part of the network completely.

- **Manipulation of software/Hardware:** It is considered a significant concern in 5G private networks as they evolve and support mission-critical applications. In these attacks, the attacker uses a rogue or fake basestation to exploit the vulnerability during device attachment and paging. One such attack is PACMAN, which utilizes the mobility-enabled malicious Wi-Fi access points to exploit the vulnerabilities in the industrial applications of 5G private networks [89].
- **Impersonate attack:** It is a key security concern in 5G private networks and can be launched on the user's equipment or mobile device. In uplink impersonation, an attacker can pretend to be a legitimate user device to send malicious data to the network. In contrast, in downlink impersonation, the attacker

acts as a legitimate network entity to whom the user device can connect [53]. The result of impersonation leads to a breach of privacy, disruption of services, and other leakage of sensitive information.

B. Threats Impact: In the second step, we present the different types of threats (identified and reviewed in the first step) with the respective impact of the attack based on the security requirements. The security requirements are related to confidentiality, integrity, and availability. The details are presented in Table 3.

C. Modeling of Threats: In the third step, we have characterized and modeled attacks on a baseline architecture. To achieve this objective, we have mapped the attack category with the attack types and provided the attack impact and entry point information. As 5G private architecture is already established, we have also correlated the different

Fig. 6. Taxonomy of the 5G private network threats mapped with layers.

5G services and 5G private architecture-supported use cases with the layered approach as presented in Table 3.

5. B5G layered architecture & enabling technologies

This section provides fundamental knowledge about the B5G/6G architecture and key enabling technologies. In [90], the study has explained the key design requirements for the future wireless network architecture, (i) Network programmability, (ii) Deployment flexibility, (iii) Simplicity and efficiency, (iv) Security, robustness & reliability, and (v) Automation. These key requirements are expected to provide intelligent network orchestration and management shortly. SDN and NFV can achieve network programmability in future wireless technology. Deployment flexibility is another key design requirement that can be achieved by container-based approaches using Docker and Kubernetes. To achieve architectural simplicity, RAN and core functions can be integrated as a single entity [90]. Automation is another key driving factor for future networks, and AI plays a significant role in achieving automation. It is expected that the future architecture will support the open network platform and provide cross-domain integration in which different vendors and service providers may be involved in network and service provisioning, which is why it is essential to map the threats to the layer of the architecture. This approach will help protect the infrastructure against emerging threats by anticipating the impact of an attack.

5.1. B5G layered architecture

Different architectures have been proposed for the B5G/6G technology using various concepts such as intelligence, IoT, and slicing-based architecture. Currently, no standardized architecture is defined for B5G/6G networks. Some existing research efforts include the 5GPP initiative on the architecture as a part of the SNS working group. SNS

identifies and captures the novel trend, a key technology enabler for realizing 5G and B5G (Beyond the 5th generation) networks [53]. A couple of research projects in B5G/6G network architectures are not limited to 6G-Flagship, Hexa-X, RISE-6G, TeraFlow, MARSAL, AI@EDGE, 6G BRAINS, REINDEER, DEDICATE-6G, DAEMON, and HORSE. The details of these projects are mentioned in [27]. For illustration, we have provided a brief overview of them.

The Hexa-x focuses on radio technology that works on high frequency, localization, and intelligent network design, whereas RISE-6G focuses on utilizing Intelligent surface (RIS) technology for radio wave propagation control to enable a sustainable and dynamic wireless environment for the B5G networks. The TeraFlow project provided the SDN controller to the B5G networks and integrated distributed computing to enable multi-tenancy. MARSAL focuses on developing the framework that manages and orchestrates the network resources in B5G networks with optical and wireless infrastructure. AI@EDGE concentrates on developing a trustworthy AI solution for managing heterogeneous mobile edge computing resources. 6G BRAINS project develops AI-driven multi-agent deep reinforcement learning solutions for resource allocation in future industrial networks. DEDICATE-6G aims to develop a smart connectivity platform using AI and blockchain technologies. The DAEMON project aims to efficiently manage the network resources using dedicated network intelligence and machine learning algorithms. In contrast, REINDEER aims to achieve zero-touch latency by creating wireless access consisting of distributed radio computing and storage resources. The HORSE project seeks to utilize the 5G concepts to define the B5G network with the help of new ideas like digital twins and AI. The 6G IoT-enabled architecture [91] shares the common layers with the Hexa-X, including the perception/infrastructure layer, the connection/network layer, and the application layer, respectively. Both architectures support network slicing, edge computing, management, and orchestration techniques and focus on diverse applications and vertical industries. The main difference is that Hexa-X architecture is more generalized and covers the entire spectrum of B5G technologies and

Fig. 7. Layered architecture for B5G/6G [91,95].

innovation, whereas the 6G-IoT architecture is more specialized and focuses on IoT needs and applications. An intelligent 6G architecture proposed by H. Yang et al. consists of four layers: the intelligent sensing layer, the data mining and analytical layer, the Intelligent control layer, and the smart application layer [92]. Each of the layers was responsible for different privacy issues. W. Wu et al. proposed an AI-enabled native 6G architecture using slicing concepts [93], to facilitate intelligent network management while supporting different AI services. The slicing architecture consisted of an infrastructure layer, a core network layer, and the AI as a service layer. “SOLID” is another intelligent architecture for 6G mobile networks [94], which addresses the legacy issues, complex operations, and maintenance issues in the previous generation 5G architecture. In addition to the traditional layers, SOLID architecture includes three layers and four planes (data collection, AI, sharing and cooperation, and security plane) respectively.

To address the RQ-2, we have looked into the existing literature to identify the known threats in the B5G/6G network, considering the layered approach of the architecture. The layered approach could help the operator and developer identify the specific attack on each layer, along with the fundamental protocols or technologies involved in impacting the B5G application. These threats range from communication and signaling attacks to malicious malware and interception attacks. To demonstrate the different threats, we have adopted the commonly involved layers in Hexa-x E2E [95] and 6G IoT-enabled architecture [91] as shown in Fig. 7. The description of each layer is presented below.

- The perception layer collects the raw data and employs the control actions from physical systems or devices by interacting with the environment. It provides the data to the network layer, which then processes and reroutes it. The perception layer is vulnerable to cyber-attacks and security risks due to the broadcast nature of communication channels and random key generation [96,97].
- The network layer provides the communication networks to the devices and user equipment for connecting devices to the edge/cloud server and transmitting data and control information. The 6G connection layer connects with the application layer through network technologies like distributed service framework, edge network, and cooperative resources, and enables the applications to ensure the ubiquitous connection and handling of increased and sensitive data traffic [98].
- The application layer encompasses software and services that interact with the connection layer to interact with external industries or services [91]. This layer is also called an edge computing system, responsible for storage, data processing, and decision-making.

For illustration, we have provided different B5G applications and associated threats to them. B5G applications range from the smart system and industrial automation to Augmented Reality (AR), Internet

Fig. 8. Threat vector for B5G networks.

of Things (IoT), Internet-of-Vehicle (IoV), Autonomous drone systems, Internet-of-Robotics-Things (IoRT), Internet-of-Medical-Things (IoMT), Industrial Internet-of-Things (IIoT), and holographic communication (HC). Many aforementioned B5G/6G applications rely on API (Application programming interface) to connect with IoT devices and other systems. The attacker can target the applications above by exploiting the vulnerabilities in the applications and communication protocols. For example, AR applications utilize sensitive and personal data; the most common threats include DoS, malware, and deepfake agents [99]. In [100], the authors analyze various potential new threats caused by introducing new technologies related to the usage of open-source tools and frameworks for B5G/6G network deployment. The study also highlights that one significant threat in IoMT is false data injection. The most common attacks on IoV include DoS attacks, eavesdropping, and jamming attacks, which result in location tracking, compromised credentials, exposure of internal vehicle sensor information, and ubiquitous data capture of public data and non-users. Moreover, the IIoT is also vulnerable to node capture attacks, DoS attacks, phishing attacks, and false data injection attacks. Furthermore, autonomous drones are susceptible to eavesdropping, spoofing, and DoS attacks. Several attack vectors can be included in HC, such as spoofing, eavesdropping, jamming, MITM, DoS, and malware attacks. The attacker can inject malicious content into the holographic data stream, leading to unauthorized access and compromising the privacy and security of the users.

5.2. Threat vector and dimensions

Inspired by the ENISA taxonomy, this section provides an overview of threat categorization, characterization, and modeling that occurs across the different layers of the B5G architecture using a three-step approach. The structure and foundation of threat classification are shown in Fig. 8. The term taxonomy in our work refers to a structured, hierarchical classification of B5G threats based on the impact of the attack. As highlighted previously, this layered approach has been adopted by Farooqui et al. [14], to represent the identified threats in a single category by the architecture layers and key enabling technologies. To characterize and model this, a baseline architecture, adopted from the Hexa-x E2E and 6G-IoT-enabled architecture, better reflects the attacks concerning the architecture layers. The architecture layers include the perception/infrastructure, connection/network, and application/service layers, where the attacks can be mapped. Various attacks related to the B5G network architecture layers are described below.

- The physical layer encompasses all the threats related to physical technologies such as m-MIMO, THz communication, VLC, and IRS technology that impact the physical system or end devices connected with the B5G network.
- The connection layer encompasses all the threats related to programmability, virtualization, and slicing that impact the IoT communication system, base station, network functions, and operations.

- The application layer encompasses the threats associated with B5G applications and services. The application layer supports integrating different applications with AI and ML and relies on an open API interface. This layer encompasses the threats that impact end users, IoT edge computing systems, and application servers.

5.3. Enabling technologies

In this section, we have provided a list of key enabling technologies that are possible with the B5G/6G networks, including (i) THz communication, (ii) Advanced antenna technologies, (iii) small cell deployment, (iv) aerial and Aerial Communication, (v) Edge computing and Distributed Networking. The overview of key technologies is provided in Fig. 9. Moreover, detailed information about different communication technologies is presented along with their security risks and attacks. The details of these key technologies are given below.

- *THz Communication*: Explores the terahertz (THz) frequency spectrum within the 0.1 THz to 10 THz range. The technology is considered to improve the signal quality of the B5G/6G networks, as it promotes ultra-low latency and exceptional reliability. THz communication is projected to facilitate increased bandwidth, exceptionally high data transmission rates, capacity, and secure data transmission. Despite the advantages, THz transmission generates high propagation loss and can be compromised by access control attacks, active eavesdropping, data, and power leakage [101]. THz waves tend to propagate linearly without bending or diffracting, in contrast to conventional radio waves [102]. Therefore, THz waves cannot propagate for a longer distance than mm-wave signals because of their high frequency and atmospheric absorption. Furthermore, THz communication is also associated with 'path loss', 'atmosphere loss', energy loss, and 'interference issues that can cause weaker signals or data transmission security' [103].
 - *Advanced Antenna Technologies*: Plays a crucial role in the physical layer of B5G communication. Beyond m-MIMO, the technology leverages IRS (Intelligent Reflecting Surface) technology and other novel antenna designs to improve the physical layer's signal efficiency, coverage capacity, and security. Despite the advantages of advanced antenna technologies, the IRS technology is vulnerable to eavesdropping threats and impacts the privacy and integrity of data transmission [104]. Moreover, cell-free massive MIMO (CF-mMIMO) in B5G networks is used to connect the antennas with the central processing unit that manages the transmission and reception of signals to improve the speed, capacity, and reliability of wireless networks. Despite having the spectral efficiency of CF-mMIMO, they are considered targets by malicious eavesdroppers, especially active attackers [105]. In CF-m-MIMO, pilot spoofing and pilot contamination attacks play a vital role as they can cause incorrect channel state information (CSI) estimation. Active eavesdropping forward uplink sequence interferes with the pilot training phase and affects the downlink transmission for stealing the authorized information [106].
 - *Deployment of Small cell*: B5G network will mostly be built upon 5G networks with the advancement of nano cells, quantum cells, terahertz cells, and aerial and satellite cells. These cell structures are designed to meet the growing demands of the hyper-connected future while introducing new design vulnerabilities. Molecular communication (MC) utilizes the nano cells and THz frequencies to enhance the coverage and capacity of densely populated areas that are impossible with traditional communication systems, such as biological systems, underwater communication, and highly dense nano networks. These cells provide localized connectivity and support a massive number of devices with ultra-low latency requirements. More specifically, deploying nano cells in MC increases several security issues [107].
- Another deployment of small cells is quantum communication (QC), which is used in 5G wireless networks to provide coverage capacity, high data rates, and improve long-distance communication. In QC quantum cells are utilized through quantum key distribution (QKD). The QKD is used to secure communication, encryption of data, and address the inherent security flaws in traditional networks [108]. The data is encoded into the quantum state, making it difficult for the attacker to clone it. It is particularly useful against eavesdropping attacks. The main problem with QC is the implementation flaws, and if the keys are not correctly managed, it will lead to unauthorized access to sensitive information [109]. The development of quantum cells is at a very early stage. There is a need to have a robust security framework and protocols designed for QC that will be essential for the mitigation of potential threats and ensuring the reliability of quantum cells in B5G/6G networks [110].
- *Satellite and Aerial Communication*: B5G/6G network can be integrated into non-terrestrial networks (NTN) (e.g. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), high altitude platform stations (HAPS), drones, and satellites) to provide connectivity in areas with insufficient coverage, especially in remote areas. Despite having the advantage NTN faces different challenges related to deployment and management [111]. Moreover, the dynamic nature of NTN introduces additional problems such as signal propagation, interference, and handover management [112]. An attacker can potentially intercept and decode the signal transmitted between the satellite and the users, thereby gaining access to the data being transmitted [25]. For example, when a user's equipment (UE) moves from one cell to another. The handover might be unsuccessful, the user call may get terminated, and the quality of service (QoS) may also be reduced. In the context of the security issue, signaling threats or eavesdropping are a major concern in NTN due to the open nature of wireless communication. Although the satellite and aerial cell can extend the connectivity to regions beyond the reach of the terrestrial cell but have their security challenges related to jamming, spoofing, and physical attack on the aerial infrastructure [113].
 - *Intelligent radio (IR)*: is considered a prominent technology in the physical layer that provides self-adoptive, self-optimizing, and context-aware radio access solutions. Malicious attacks can be eavesdropped on IR via wireless channels, such as DoS, spoofing, and malicious data injection, causing issues in the AI model. The 6G radio interface uses technologies like m-MIMO to reduce the interference between the cells and direct beaming to enhance the performance. The radio interface is vulnerable to different attacks such as eavesdropping (active and passive, spoofing (identity spoofing, Sybil and pilot spoofing attacks, jamming (reactive, pilot, and proactive, and contamination (pilot and feedback) attacks [114].
 - *Advanced Network Protocols*: New protocols may need to be developed to handle the complexity and demands of B5G/6G, particularly for supporting massive IoT deployments and ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC). Authentication and key agreement (AKA) protocol leads to impersonation and packet replay attacks, resulting in compromising the confidentiality and integrity [115].
 - *Software-Defined Networking*: In B5G/6G networks, two versions of the SDN were proposed, software-defined wide area network (SD-WAN) and software-defined local area network (SD-LAN). Despite the advantages, SDN is vulnerable to various attacks such as host-based attacks, IP spoofing, flow table overloading, DDoS, control plane saturation, and hijacking [116].
 - *Network Slicing and Virtualization*: In a B5G-based network, the sub-networks allow the customization of network resources using network slicing techniques to meet the diverse requirements of the various applications. NFV enables the creation of virtual

resources, improves flexibility in deploying the network slices, and facilitates the integration of diverse communication, sensing, and localization services. Despite having the benefits, NFV is vulnerable to various attacks, NFV managers are also susceptible to eavesdropping, flooding, side-channel attacks, and DDoS attacks [45]. B5G/6G Network slicing is categorized into intra-slicing and inter-slicing attacks. In an intra-slicing application, the attacker and target belong to the same network slice. In contrast, in an inter-slicing application, the attacker and target belong to different slices [117]. However, unauthorized persons can take remote control access to sub-network functions, novel applications, and external communication interfaces to impose vulnerabilities in deep slicing, leading to jamming attacks, spoofing, and DoS/DDoS attacks [118]. In the context of AI native networks, slicing also faces many threats, such as misconfiguration of the slice, theft of the slice, and misuse of the slice, including AI-based attacks used for intelligent network management.

- *Edge computing*: Integration of AI with 5G and B5G networks, also known as edge intelligence (EI). In B5G networks, moving the data processing tasks closer to the edge rather than to a central cloud is essential. The edge server collects data from nearby devices and shares it collaboratively with the ML models. However, the data is collected from multiple sources, and the outcome of the AI/ML model is highly data-dependent. EI is linked to different security attacks and risks. The most common attacks on them include MITM attacks and DDoS attacks [119].
- *Distributed Networking*: Distributed networking in B5G/6G refers to the network architecture that distributes the network functions and resources across a wide geographical area. Unlike traditional networking, where the processing is done at a central location, distributed networking decentralizes the network functions to improve scalability and reliability, reducing latency and dependency on centralized infrastructure. Automated and distributed services [120] introduce several attacks in the micro-granular layer. Particularly, automation has led to some privacy concerns due to incorporating a dense variety of 5 G applications.
- *AI Driven network Management*: AI enhances network management, threat detection, and incident response automation and improves system security. At the same time, AI opens the doors for adversarial attacks that can manipulate anomaly detection models. Attackers can manipulate the AI models using poisoned data, leading to incorrect decision-making or bypassing security. Moreover, the attacker can use the reverse engineering AI to predict and evade the detection algorithm or mechanism.
- *Container-based virtualization*: Plays a vital role in B5G/6G networks by enabling the efficient deployment and management of network functions and services. The attacker could exploit the vulnerability to the internal VM (virtual machine) switch used for the communication of two VMs, or use a direct attack by hacking the existing VM to use it as an intermediate port for the attacker's vRAN/vCore. The impact of this type of attack will result from rooting, DoS, packet sniffing, and malicious code propagation to the side-channel attacks on vRAN/vCore within the virtualized system [100].
- *Management and Orchestration*: Mainly, two components are involved in M&O [121]: closed-loop automation and intent-based interface (IBI). Although these components enable the dynamic and adaptive control of network services and resources, several security attacks are associated with deploying management and orchestration. Security threats to closed-loop automation include DDoS, MITM, and Deception attacks. Moreover, an Intent-based interface (IBI) used for the deployment of B5G infrastructure is vulnerable to information exposure, undesirable configuration, and abnormal behavior attacks, leading to additional compromises and assaults on the security goals of the system.

- *Heterogeneous Cloud*: Cloud transformation in B5G/6G is done using the concept "Het-Cloud" [90]. Het-cloud enabled the services in B5G/6G networks such as AI/ML processing, immersive experiences, edge computing, and other distributed computing tasks. The most common security issues related to heterogeneous cloud include: unauthorized access, violation of access control policies, data privacy breaches, insecure interfaces and APIs, malicious attacks, DoS attacks, and loss of data [122]. Heterogeneity is also linked to information leakage for the various 5G and B5G applications, including smart healthcare, where the risk is very high if sensitive information like patient records, treatment, and specifications are not adequately protected.

A. Categorization of Security Threats: The first is to classify the identified threats under a single category to present the different threats on a baseline B5G/6G architecture. Fig. 10 (<https://bit.ly/3IFHKEW> accessed on 26 July 2025) classifies the threats into various categories, whereas Fig. 12 (<https://bit.ly/3INJNNx> accessed on 26 July 2025), maps the threats with the layers of the architecture. The detailed information about the characterization and modeling of identified attacks concerning the layers of the architecture is presented in Table 4. The description of each threat category is mentioned below.

- *RAN threats*: In 5G and B5G networks, RAN faces various security threats in B5G networks due to the complex architecture and open interfaces. The security attacks include a rough basestation, a fake basestation, and a compromised UE. One common attack on RAN is the DoS (Denial of Service) attack, in which the attacker targets the radio resource control (RRC) to establish a flooding of traffic, leading to resource exhaustion and disruption of operations [130]. Moreover, the implementation of open RAN (O-RAN) interfaces has led to the introduction of vulnerabilities related to supply chain attacks.
- *Edge computing threats*: It plays a vital role in a heterogeneous decentralized environment in B5G/6G. The decentralized infrastructure of MEC makes it vulnerable to various network attacks targeting the edge nodes, such as data tampering, unauthorized access attacks, DoS/DDoS, impersonation-based attacks, session hijacking, and disclosure of sensitive information. MEC relies on local processing, making it susceptible to interception if encryption and authentication are weak. Moreover, if the edge server is compromised, it could affect multiple users and applications. In [131], the authors highlight the edge learning vulnerabilities of the 6G-IoT systems, including backdoor attacks, adversarial attacks, poisoning attacks, evasion attacks, and many privacy-related attacks.
- *SDN/NFV exploitation attacks*: In B5G-based networks, Software-defined Wide Area Networks (SD-WAN) are utilized and are considered vulnerable to various security attacks such as DoS or DDoS, MITM, ARP spoofing, and insider adversaries, which compromise communication between the SDN switches and controllers or overwhelm the flow table storage capacity [116].
- *Slicing attacks*: The concept of slicing in 5G and B5G networks increases the risks of inter-slice attacks, cross-slice attacks, and misconfiguration attacks. Inter-slice attacks are where an attacker in one slice tries to compromise the other slice. Cross-slice attacks mostly occur where the isolation mechanism is weak between the slices, and the attacker can exploit the vulnerabilities in one slice and attempt to compromise the other slice. Moreover, improper configuration can lead to security challenges, such as misconfiguration attacks [45].
- *AI/ML-based attacks*: Integration of AI/ML in 5G and B5G is linked with various attacks such as poisoning, evasion, adversarial, and other API based attacks [124]. The detailed information on these threats can be found in Section 7.1.

Fig. 9. Key enablers of B5G/6G networks.

- **Molecular communication attacks:** Molecular communication is a key technology utilized in 5G and B5G networks, and a couple of security attacks are associated with MC. In [132], the study discusses various types of threats at different levels of MC, including flooding attacks, jamming, and desynchronization.
- **Quantum communication attacks:** It is a key technology that utilizes QKD to secure communication. The attacker can exploit the vulnerabilities in the QKD systems to launch side-channel and other unauthorized access-related attacks. In [133], the research has indicated how a signal photon detector can be exploited through radio frequency (RF) radiation, allowing the attacker to intercept the quantum key transmission from a distance.
- **Malicious Code/Software:** Malicious code or software represents considerable risks to the B5G networks due to vulnerabilities generated by the rapid advancement in wireless communication systems. Integrating machine learning with the B5G networks aims to enhance the network's performance but exposes vulnerability by using malware, spyware, and other ransomware-related attacks impacting the integrity of the users and unavailability and destruction of the services [100].
- **Physical attack:** Theft of random keys is a significant security concern in B5G/6G wireless communication. Random keys are essential for encryption and securing communication; their theft leads to manipulation and data breaches. [123].
- **Signaling threats:** The signaling threats/storms come from the vulnerabilities in the radio technologies such as mMIMO [125], In this type of attack, the attacker disrupts communication before the establishment of communication between the two entities and is involved in key management, authentication, link creation and registration by sending an additional signal, which will put a heavy load on the base station and thus results in interruption of service
- **DoS/Jamming attack:** In a DoS attack scenario, the attacker impersonates the network devices with their IP address and injects a forged service request to inject malicious traffic with a botnet to flood the legal services. A similar attack scenario has been presented in Fig. 11(c), where the attacker can make use of the botnets to generate a larger number of requests. In this way the attacker has gained access to multiple devices that are part of the bot and controlling them to compromise the edge computing services. In [134], different types of jamming attacks are discussed, such as active, reactive, and proactive jamming. These

jamming attacks also lead to DoS attacks. In the physical layer of the future wireless communication system, the jamming attack can be performed on mmWave and NOMA networks. Consider an attack scenario, where the communication happens between two legitimate users, Bob and Alice, as shown in Fig. 11(a). The transmission signal uses a specific frequency channel to transmit the information. The attacker can inject the radio frequency (same as Bob) to occupy the shared wireless channel. Such an aggressive injection can prevent legitimate users from using the wireless channel to communicate, also called active jamming [25].

- **Eavesdropping:** It takes place when a malicious node tries to listen to the communication between the authorized nodes. In [105], authors categorize eavesdropping into three main branches: active, passive, and potential eavesdropping. In active eavesdropping, the attacker intentionally introduces noise, jamming, and disseminates false data. Meanwhile, in passive eavesdropping, the attacker passively listens to the messages without taking action. In passive eavesdropping, the attacker is within close range of the authorized node and extracts the data from the channel without inferring the communication, leading to compromise of the key distribution [96]. In potential eavesdropping, the attacker behaves like an authorized user under specific circumstances. Device tracking and interception are also significant threats where the node position is available to a third party.

Consider the scenario of passive eavesdropping; in this case, the internal eavesdropper is a legitimate NOMA cluster user with access to the same beam scope as presented in Fig. 11(b). Since the NOMA users shared the same frequency and power spectrum, the eavesdropper can wiretap by intercepting the communication meant for the other users in an identical cluster. In this way, the eavesdropper can exploit its position within the beam scope to capture and analyze the transmitted signals.

- **Spoofing attack:** Spoofing attacks or pilot spoofing attacks [78] can occur when an attacker manipulates the signal, phase, amplitude, or timing to disrupt the channel estimation phase of the transmitter. In this type of attack, the attacker sends the spoofing signal or messages with the fake identities of other wireless devices, such as MAC address, IP address, and radio frequency identification (RFID) tags of the mobile users, Base station (BS), and access point (AP) to take the illegal advantages. A similar attack scenario is presented in Fig. 11(c), where a fake edge attacker impersonates the nearby edge device by sending it fake computational results,

Fig. 10. Taxonomy of B5G Network threat categorization.

Table 4

Categories of the B5G/6G threats mapped with layers.

Attack category	Physical layer	Connection layer	Application layer
RAN Threats [76,123]	Rough Basestation Fake Basestation DoS/DDoS RAN	NA	Supply chain attack
Edge Computing attacks [123]	Data leakage Side channel attack, Spoofing attack	Session Hijacking, DoS/DDoS on edge node	Data leakage, unauthorized access, Disclosure of sensitive information.
SDN/NFV exploitation attacks [116]	Tampering SDN/NFV	SDN controller attack, Compromised VNF, Rough VNF	Malicious deployment of VNF, Unauthorized access
Slicing attacks [45]	Cross-slice attack	Inter-slice attack, Misconfigured slice	Cross-slice attack
AI/ML based attacks [124]	Poisoning attack Adversarial attacks, API-based attacks	NA	Poisoning attack Adversarial attacks, Evasion attack, API-based attacks
Molecular communication attacks [123]	Flooding/jamming Desynchronization	NA	Flooding/Jamming
Quantum communication attacks [123]	Quantum key interception Side-channel attack	NA	Side-Channel attack
Malicious code /Software [100]	Ransomware, botnet	Malicious network function, injection attack, protocol exploitation attack	Malware, spyware, Deepfake agent
Physical attack [123]	Theft of random or physical keys, Sabotage of network hardware	NA	N/A
Signaling threat [125]	Signaling threat, Signaling storm	Protocol exploitation	Signaling DoS
Denial-of-service attack [96]	Radio Jamming, Protocol-aware jamming, jamming attack (reactive /proactive/ pilot jamming), and Edge node overloaded	Flooding, DoS/DDoS attacks, resource exhaustion, flooding base station, and energy depletion attack	DoS, DoS against XR services, and flooding attack
Eavesdropping [105]	Eavesdropping (active, passive and potential eavesdropping), proactive eavesdropping, device tracking, and interception attack	Eavesdropping, IP spoofing and data interception	Misuse of security software and applications (Identity tracking, breach sensitive data personal data) phishing and social engineering attacks, API interception
Spoofing attack [126]	Signal spoofing, Sybil spoofing, and pilot spoofing attacks	Host-based spoofing attacks, impersonation attacks, DNS spoofing, data injection, and packet modification	Fake application server spoofing, false data injection, and identity spoofing attacks.
Contamination attack [127]	Pilot contamination and Feedback attacks	False pilot signal injection	N/A
Manipulation of network configuration/ Data forging [128]	Modify sensor information, injecting false data, stealthy attacks, meta-surface manipulation	Network misconfiguration attacks, protocol manipulation, DNS manipulation, routing table manipulation, misconfiguration or poorly configured network/services	Interception and modifying attacks, data positioning attack
Unauthorized access [119]	MITM, data leakage, injecting false data, location exposure, and erroneous information to the receiver	Unauthorized access to base station MITM attack, Session hijacking, traffic sniffing, data breaches, data tampering, and insider attack	Session hijacking, MITM, False data injection, deception attack, replay attack, and fake beacon messages create virtual traffic jams
Hardware/Software Manipulation [129]	Side channel attack, hardware manipulation, and compromised UE	False or fake base station, false gateways	Side channel attack

and a rough access point (AP) attacker can access the data of the mobile users.

- **Contamination attack:** A special type of attack in a B5G network where the attacker deliberately sends or injects false data into the network is called a contamination attack. A pilot contamination attack (PCA) is a specific threat to the 6G-IoT network in which the attacker transmits the identical pilot sequences as the legitimate user to disrupt user detection and channel estimation [127].

PCA primarily occurs on a physical layer of wireless communication systems, like m-MIMO or beam-forming systems. Ultra-massive MIMO and Multi-user MIMO are more susceptible to PCA. In these systems, pilot signals are used for channel estimation and user identification, crucial for effectively transmitting the data. During the uplink process, the user (Bob) transmits the pilot signal to the base station, which uses this information to estimate the channel condition and direct the downlink beam toward Bob as presented in Fig. 11(d). An eavesdropper (Eve) manages to send

fake signals (spoofing uplink signals) during the uplink process, causing the base station to think Eve is Bob. The Base station directs the downlink beam to Eve, allowing it to intercept the communication meant for Bob [25].

- **Manipulate network configuration/Data forging:** AI in B5G can lead to a significant concern for the forging attack, where the attacker maliciously alters the data to deceive the system or users. The data forging attack can target the large amount of data processed by the AI applications in the B5G network. These attacks can compromise the integrity and reliability of the information, affecting the quality of intelligent services like indoor positioning or autonomous vehicles in B5G networks [128]. A scenario presented in Fig. 11(e), where the attacker embedded the malicious content during the training phase of the model, leads to inaccurate prediction of the attack or incorrect decision making.
- **Unauthorized access:** The most common attacks on the transmission status of communication channels include MITM, injecting false data, traffic sniffing, and data tampering attacks, which lead to data leakage [119]. In this attack type, the attacker eavesdrops on the transmission, intercepts the communication between the two legitimate parties, and injects the manipulated messages into the B5G system to the device or even controls the radio device. Consider the example of the MITM attack in the mmWave system presented in Fig. 11(c), where the attacker intercepts the messages of the transmitter, replaces and modifies the intercepted message with the fake one, and then sends it back to the receiver.
- **Hardware/Software Manipulation:** Towards deploying the B5G/6G network, hardware manipulation threats become a significant concern. Threats related to hardware manipulation involve the intentional modification or sabotage of physical components in the network infrastructure, which can lead to serious security vulnerabilities. These vulnerabilities also facilitate side-channel attacks. As the technology progresses toward B5G, fake base stations still exist in the 6G network, posing a serious security threat as they collect user information and launch a DoS attack [129]. Hardware manipulation has an impact on user data and the integrity of the network.

B. Threat's impact: In the second step, we have presented different types of threats based on the specific impact of the attack on security requirements, including confidentiality, integrity, and availability (as shown in Fig. 13). Detailed information about the threats impacting security requirements related to confidentiality, integrity, and availability and their solutions in B5G is mentioned below.

Confidentiality: is related to data confidentiality and privacy. Data confidentiality mainly helps fight against passive attacks, and privacy prevents unauthorized users from analyzing or influencing the data. Homomorphic encryption is expected to be a key technology for preserving data confidentiality and privacy in B5G networks [137]. Cryptographic schemes such as digital signatures and certificates can restrict unauthorized user access to secure data confidentiality. Quantum-safe cryptographic schemes can also be considered a prospective solution to secure communication in B5G/6G networks. Jamming and eavesdropping attacks nearly impact every B5G application. The result of eavesdropping compromises confidentiality through the data transmission on an unsecured channel. B5G/6G physical key generation is also used to protect the confidentiality of the communication between the UE and the base station from eavesdropping and jamming attacks. More specifically, m-MIMO leverages to mitigate both active and passive eavesdropping.

Availability is defined as the service or resource that is accessible and usable to a user anywhere and anytime. It is a measure of how robust a service is against any attack. For example, DoS and DDoS are the most common attacks in B5G networks that violate the availability of the network. In the infrastructure layer, jamming attacks are also used to disrupt the communication capabilities of the network by overwhelming the interferences or by adding noise [96]. For this purpose,

the attacker could transfer the radio signal continuously on the wireless channel to disrupt the communication by decreasing the signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio. This leads to the DoS attack at the physical layer. With the increased number of connected devices and heterogeneity, it will be very difficult to fight against jamming and DoS attacks to maintain the availability of the B5G wireless network.

Integrity: Currently, there is no such mechanism that can avoid duplication and modification of the message, even if the message authentication mechanism confirms the source of the message. The B5G network aims to provide the availability to the different applications integral to human life such as e-health monitoring, autonomous vehicles, and immersive augmented reality. Distributed ledger technology (DLT) is considered a prospective solution to preserve the confidentiality and integrity of the B5G networks [138]. The important aspect of security in these applications of B5G is related to data integrity. The integrity ensures that the attacker cannot edit, modify, or copy messages.

C. Modeling of Threats: As highlighted previously we have a baseline layered architecture based on a B5G network. In the third step, we have provided the modeling of different types of threats identified in the previous step and modeled them with the adopted layered architecture. The modeling offers information about the various types of attacks, the entry points that can be used to launch the attack, the impact of an attack, and the respective layer involved in executing the threats, as shown in Table 5.

6. Overview of datasets

In this section, we discuss the different anomaly detection datasets used to detect and predict attacks in 5G and B5G networks. In addition, we have provided a list of challenges that are possible with the classical datasets and need to have specific 5G-related datasets.

6.1. Classical dataset

In the current state-of-the-art, different datasets are available for detecting and preventing cyber-attacks. Notable datasets include 5G NIDD, IoT-23, CSE-CIC-IDS2018, CIC-DoS 2019, BoT-IoT, and UNSW-NB15. Among these, CSE-CIC-IDS2018 [139] and CIC-DoS 2019 [140] are the two prominent datasets in cybersecurity. CSE-CIC-IDS2018 is primarily used to train the machine learning model and evaluate the effectiveness of the intrusion detection system (IDS). In contrast, CIC-DoS 2019 is used in pattern recognition and anomaly detection.

The wireless sensor network plays a crucial role in 5G networks, enabling applications such as smart cities, healthcare, and environmental monitoring. In the context of 5G WSNs, different public datasets have been listed in existing literature, including information about the network topology, sensor-related data, and other traffic patterns. WSN-DS (wireless sensor network dataset) is a prominent dataset in WSN that has been utilized to detect intrusion. The authors in [141] utilized this dataset to detect jamming attacks in multi-stage attack scenarios. The study classified different jamming attacks into constant, random, deceptive, and reactive jamming. Another important dataset is BoT-IoT [142], created to address the security challenges related to the IoT environment. This dataset includes normal and different cyber-attack flows. The dataset contains 46 features and five types of classes, one for the normal flow and four for different attack types, including DoS, DDoS, surveillance, and information theft. IoT-23 [143] is a semi-structured dataset containing log information from malicious and benign IoT network traffic packets. The dataset was created by Avast AIC laboratory using different IoT devices. The dataset consists of real data and labeled instances of IoT malware infection, three captures for the benign IoT devices, and 20 captures for the malware traffic. CIC-IoT 23 [144] is another important dataset based on IoT traffic, developed by the Brunswick Center of cybersecurity. The dataset encompasses 33 distinct features and 46 attributes, organized into seven main classes. The dataset includes both normal as well as malicious traffic associated

Fig. 11. Security threats in B5G/6G scenarios [25,135,136].

with 105 unique IoT devices. This type of variety can be linked with the heterogeneity of 5G and 6G networks. Furthermore, the dataset encapsulates the architecture of IoT networks and the various types of attacks, reflecting the complexities inherent in the 6G networks. Lastly, the Edge-IIoTset dataset [145] is a comprehensive cybersecurity dataset for IoT and IIoT applications. The data is generated from an IoT/IIoT testbed with a large representative set of devices, sensors, protocols, and cloud/edge configurations. Fourteen IoT and IIoT network attacks are identified and analyzed, categorized into five threats: DoS/DDoS attacks, information gathering, man-in-the-middle attacks, injection attacks, and malware attacks. Different studies mentioned in [146,147] have used these datasets (Edge IIoTset and IoT-23) for network traffic analysis, malware, and attack detection. The network traffic information can be extracted in a semi-structured file using Wireshark and tcpdump in .pcap files.

NSL-KDD [148] is another dataset that can be used to detect anomalies in a 5G network. Similarly, UNSW-NB15 [149] dataset contains

information on normal and attack traffic. The attacks contain generic, exploit, fuzzers, DoS, reconnaissance, analysis, backdoors, shell code, and worms. It includes 49 different features and it comprises more than 2 million records stored in different CSV format files. The authors in [150] utilized NSL-KDD and UNSW-NB15 datasets to detect anomalies. They have used deep learning approaches, such as CNN and the Bidirectional LSTM model, to classify normal traffic from attack traffic. UNSW-NB15 is a dataset based on TCP, UDP, and other protocols, whereas 5G NIDD [151] is a new dataset based on 5G network traffic records.

6.1.1. Challenges with classical datasets

Devices in 5G do not require traditional IP-based data transfer, particularly for IoT applications. So, a non-IP data delivery-based dataset was required in 5G for several reasons. Moreover, existing literature lacks DoS/DDoS-related datasets, particularly related to 5G-based network slicing. In addition, 5 G-related cyberattacks (especially on 5G

Fig. 12. Taxonomy of the B5G network threats mapped with layers.

Confidentiality	Availability	Integrity
Eavesdropping	DoS/DDoS	Session hijacking
Man-in-the-Middle	Jamming	Data tempering
Location tracking	Redirecting	Alteration/Manipulation
Impersonate	Flooding attack	Data breach
Data leakage	Signaling threats	Unauthorized access
Sniffing/Spoofing	Contamination attack	Side channel attack

Fig. 13. Overview of threat's impact with security requirements.

Core) and the sensitive nature of such data are not publicly available. This section presents an overview of open-source software for developing and testing 5G networks. We have also highlighted the security challenges associated with their deployment and implementation. These open-source software are used for RAN and Core components in different projects and test beds for the development, experimentation, and deployment of 4G and 5G mobile networks.

6.2. 5G specific dataset

This section presents a list of datasets used to detect abnormal network behavior and anomalies in 5G-based network slicing, Wi-Fi networks, and WLAN networks, which are presented below. The details of these newly created datasets have been presented in Table 6 for detecting and preventing cyber-attacks in 5G and beyond 5G networks.

Table 5
Modeling of threats with threats impact, entry points, and the layer being involved.

Attack category	Attack types	Impact	Entry points	Affected layer
Denial-of-service attack	Radio jamming [25]	Availability (disrupt legitimate communication and Jamming of particular frequencies, jamming of communication channels)	Communication channels, during RF transmitter and receiver	Perception layer
	Jamming [97] Protocol-aware jamming, reactive jamming [25]		No standardized protocol Open protocol, system broadcasting	Application layer
	DoS/ DDoS, and flooding attack [96]	Unavailability of resources and services	Access points, wireless channels, wireless clients, wireless infrastructure, Open API access	Perception layer
	DoS depletion attack [46]	Disable a battery-powered device, Availability of battery-powered devices	DNS server, storage area	Application and perception layer
Signaling threat	Energy depletion attacks [46]	Availability	Weak authentication mechanism	Connection layer
	Signaling storm [90]	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability	Cloud, radio access network, and communication links	Perception layer
	Signaling DoS [90]	Availability (overload and disruption of services)	Communication protocol	Application layer
Eavesdropping	Active eavesdropping, Passive eavesdropping, & Potential eavesdropping [105]	Privacy violation, availability (unavailability of services, disruption of legitimate communication), and confidentiality	Communication channels, insecure wireless network, compromised network infrastructure, and broadcast method	Perception, Connection, and Application
Spoofing attack	Pilot spoofing attack [114]	Confidentiality (Information leakage during downlink transmission) integrity (compromising the legitimate communication)	Communication channel	Perception layer
	Signal spoofing [43]	Disrupt and intercept the communication and manipulate the footage	Server/network functions	Perception layer
Contamination attack	Pilot contamination attack, Feedback attack [114]	Confidentiality, integrity, Availability	pilot signal transmission	Perception layer
Unauthorized access	Side channel attack, Data tampering, Insider attack [119]	Compromising confidentiality, Integrity, Authentication and authorization issues, and other related to privacy	Core network, security software, storage area, network server	Connection layer
	MITM attack, Information leakage Impersonation, and biometric data leakage [119]		API exposes, network access, misconfiguration, weak security mechanism	Perception, Connection, and Application layer
Physical attack	Unauthorized physical access to the base station, theft of key [123]	Compromising integrity, availability (disruption of radio frequency signal)	Exploiting communication protocol, weak authentication mechanism	Perception, Connection layer
Manipulation of network configuration	DNS manipulation, Data tampering, Malicious network function registration, Exploitation of misconfigured data [128]	Compromising integrity, availability (disruption of radio frequency signal)	SD-WAN controller, Network functions, DNS servers, Network management & orchestrator	Perception, Connection layer
Malicious code	Injection attacks, Malware, Spyware, Ransomware-related, and Botnet attacks [100]	Compromising integrity, Disruption of services	Storage server network functions	Application layer
Hardware Manipulation	Side-channel attack, false gateway, fake base station, compromise UE [129]	User data, integrity of the network	Virtual machines, Network functions, SD-WAN controller, user devices	Perception, Connection Application layer

- **AWID3 Dataset:** is particularly developed for the anomaly detection task in wireless networks. The dataset contains both extracted features in the CSV format and the raw pcap files publicly available on the [152]. It categorizes the attack into four main categories. i) Attack specific to 802.11, ii) attack against the local node, iii) attack against an external node, and (iv) multi-layer attack. This dataset is also used in machine learning-based wireless intrusion detection systems to identify flooding, impersonation, and injection attacks in Wi-Fi networks. Additionally, the dataset includes several assaults common to IEEE 802.3 networks, making it suitable for attacks in both wireless and wired networks. This dataset can be used to evaluate intrusion detection systems

(IDS) in the IEEE 802.1X extensible authentication protocol (EAP) environment.

Uszko et al. [153] developed a methodology to detect attacks occurring in the 5G network using the AWID3 dataset to train and test the system. The authors use the rules-based and machine learning approaches to detect the known and emerging nature of the attacks. The proposed methodology consists of both the packet inspection and rules-based modules. The utilization of both rule-based detection and machine learning makes this architecture quite reliable for the detection of both known and unknown attacks occurring in the 5G infrastructure. Their research used the AWID3 dataset to train and test the system.

Table 6

Datasets used as a benchmark experiment in the evaluation of 5G network/system.

Dataset	Attack category	Attack type	Targeted use case	System
AWID3	Wi-Fi attack	Beacon Flood, DE authentication attacks	Detection of anomalies	5G WLAN [153]
	Wi-Fi network	Flooding attack, impersonation, and injection attack	Detection of attack	Online learning [154]
5GAD-2022	5G core network attack	Reconnaissance, AMF	Detection of network-based attack	5G Core [155]
5G NIDD	IoT-related attack (Non-IP Data Delivery)	Data leakage	Detection of anomalies in NIDD	NIDD for IoT [156]
5GC PFCP	PFCP attack	4 types of PFCP-related traffic flood	Detection of attacks on 5G core PFCP traffic	5G core [157]
DoS/DDoS Attacks on 5G Network Slices	5G network slicing attack	DoS/DDoS attacks on a specific slice	Ensure the security of 5G network slicing	5G network slicing [39]
NCSRD-DS-5GDDoS	5G-based DDoS attack	DDoS, Botnets, and volume-based attacks	Detection of DDoS in 5G network environment	5G core and network [158]

- DoS/DDoS Attack Dataset:** is a dataset created by injecting various benign and attack traffic (DoS/DDoS) into the network slices within a simulated 5G network slicing testbed environment. This dataset is publicly available on IEEE DataPort [159]. Open-source software, Free5GC and UERANSIM simulators were used to create network slices. Benign traffic includes network traces of ICMP ping, ACK scan, UDP scan, SYN scan, FIN, PUSH, and URG scan. While the DoS/DDoS traffic was generated using the hping3 tool UDP flooding, TCP sync attack, TCP push, TCP fin, and TCP start to generate DOS/DDoS traffic. In [39], the authors utilized 11 features for the analysis, including flow duration, destination IP, source port, and more. A significant feature called 'slice' was also introduced to represent the specific network slice. By employing a bidirectional LSTM model, the author has classified normal traffic from malicious DoS traffic. The dataset can classify benign traffic from DoS/DDoS traffic.
- 5G-SliciNdd Dataset:** is a more generic dataset covering the global 5G network traffic and covering different types of network behavior and anomalies (based on the slice types, e.g., eMBB, mMTC, URLLC), not just DDoS-related attack information. It is designed to provide a more comprehensive view of anomalies and intrusion detection in 5G network slicing and can be accessed on Figshare [160]. The study presented in [161] utilizes the 5G-SliciNdd dataset to obtain optimal feature selection for the detection of attacks to improve the classification efficiency of the model.
- The 5GAD-2022 Attack Detection:** is another publicly available dataset on the GitHub repository, that contains 5G network traffic, including both the normal traffic and malicious traffic. The data was generated in a simulated environment by using open-source software named UERANSIM and Free5Gcore [162]. The data includes IP and slice-specific traffic. Normal traffic is categorized into two types: data collected from one UE and data collected using two UEs. The malicious data is divided into ten different types of attacks, which fall under three main categories: reconnaissance, denial-of-service, and network reconfiguration. The primary focus of the dataset is the detection of anomalies in network slicing.
- 5G NIDD Dataset :** has a focus on delivering non-IP data (IoT and low latency traffic) within a 5G environment. It is developed for the malware traffic across various network protocols in 5G. It was generated from the actual mobile devices rather than simulated traffic and can be downloaded from the IEEE DataPort [163]. The dataset includes both the normal and attack traffic, featuring 8 different types of attacks such as UDP flood, HTTP flood, slow rate DoS, TCP connect Scan, SYN scan, UDP scan, SYN flood, and ICMP. Malicious and other benign traffic is distributed throughout this dataset. This variety of segments provides comprehensive information to the researcher interested in network security and intrusion detection systems within 5G networks. This dataset is particularly useful for developing effective intrusion detection models and addressing the security challenges associated with diverse 5G network traffic profiles.
- 5GC PFCP:** also known as intrusion detection dataset in which different cyber-attacks are emulated by using k3Y again, Packet Forwarding Control Protocol (PFCP) between the session management function (SMF) and user plane function (UPF). To generate this dataset, a testbed was created using twelve dockerized 5G functions emulated using open5GC and UERANSIM. The dataset is publicly available [157] and helps identify the vulnerabilities to the 5G core, particularly DoS attacks. The dataset includes network function virtualized gNodeB (gNB), and a cyber-attack impersonating the maliciously instantiated SMF. The particular cyber-attacks include PFCP session establishment DoS attack, PFCP session Deletion DoS attack, PFCP session modification DoS attack (DROP apply action), and PFCP session modification DoS attack (DUPL apply action). The PFCP attacks were executed, and for each attack, PCAP files were maintained with the transmission control protocol (TCP)/Internet Protocol (IP) and network flow traffic and PFCP flow statistics. The TCP/IP network flow statistics were produced by using CICFlowMeter, and PFCP flow statistics were generated using a custom PFCP Flow Generator. The network data of each device and entity was captured by Tshark for each network function and radio element, respectively. The dataset can support the development of a detection system tailored to a 5 G-based system.
- NCSRD-DS-5G DDoS:** is another dataset obtained from a real-world 5G testbed, is specifically designed for the analysis of DDoS attacks, and is available in [158]. The dataset was created using 5Gtestbed aligned with 3GPP standards, capturing both the benign and attack traffic within the 5G network. The benign traffic includes normal activities like users engaging in streaming YouTube content, whereas the malicious users engage in performing Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, specifically UDP floods facilitated by hping3. The dataset captures both the radio and core metrics information, including uplink/downlink

bitrates, retransmission, and session establishment metrics of the 5G network. This dataset can be used to see how the DDoS attack can be mitigated in the 5G infrastructure.

7. AI/ML in 5G and B5G networks

AI plays a critical role in 5G and B5G networks, not only in the design and optimization of protocols and operations, but also in the design of early detection of threats and anomalies. Integrating AI with the B5G network presents a double-edged nature, as it can also become a target of attacks and a potential solution for mitigating attacks. Unlike the traditional 5G networks, where security solutions across all devices and base stations are configured with universal settings for certain types of attacks, it is apparent that such an approach cannot be applied in B5G networks. Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) have been extensively used, but it is demonstrated that they fail in the detection of complex attacks. Nowadays, 5G networks are utilized by different machine learning (ML) algorithms to achieve dynamic and robust security mechanisms [164,165] to overcome their limitations in the detection of complex and zero-day attacks. Initially, signature-based and anomaly-based detection systems made extensive use of classical ML techniques; however, they lack automatic feature engineering, have a low detection rate, and are not efficient in detecting small variants of existing attacks. The research has shifted toward deep learning (DL) based solutions due to the increasing complexity of hacking incidents, zero-day attacks, and unknown malware. Cybersecurity attacks on B5G networks are dynamic, polymorphic, and sophisticated, using previously unseen custom code, able to communicate with external command and control entities to update their functionality. To detect cyber-attacks in B5G networks, IDS utilized both the ML and DL models to achieve a higher detection rate [166]. Moreover, the distributed learning models, deep reinforcement learning (DRL) [167], and federated learning (FL) [168] have proven their ability to detect complex attacks and zero-day attacks in distributed environments. The FL-based solutions keep data in the user's proximity compared to cloud-based centralized learning to enhance data privacy and location privacy.

7.1. AI as a threat vector in 5G and B5G networks

In this subsection, we focus on the role of AI as a weapon and a target for the different threats against the infrastructure. More specifically, we elaborate on the following attacks on AI key areas:

- **Adversarial Machine learning (AML):** We have highlighted how AI systems are particularly vulnerable to adversarial inputs that mislead the AI-based intrusion detection system (IDS). In the existing literature, three main attacks that target the AI system include (i) data positioning, (ii) algorithm positioning attack, and (iii) model positioning attack. The positioning attack aims to insert wrong-labeled data in the dataset or change the input objects to mislead the ML algorithm. Algorithm poisoning is done by influencing the distributed learning process of an algorithm by uploading a manipulated weight to the local learning model, and model poisoning is done by replacing the deployed model with a malicious one. Data positioning attacks are more challenging than the input objects are accessible in the outer environment, and the attacker can easily make intelligent settings to carry out their intention [124].
- **Poisoning attacks:** Influence the learning phase of an ML system, which leads the model to learn inaccurately. For example, data injection, data manipulation, and logic corruption are some of the poisoning attacks. Adding malicious content to the data during the training phase of the data results in an influence on the integrity of the model. More specifically, poisonous attacks involve the manipulation of data during the training phase to produce a biased or incorrect model. In [169], the author has utilized

the label-flipped attack to generate a data poisoning attack and a stealthy model positioning method for a model poisoning attack. In [170], the author used a local model poisoning attack that manipulated the local model sent from the compromised worker device to the master device.

- **Evasion attacks:** Defeat the learning models or disrupt the testing data by injecting faults into the data. These attacks also avoid the model during the inference phase using carefully designed adversarial examples [124].
- **API-based attacks:** Are mainly categorized into: (i) model inversion, (ii) model extraction, and (iii) membership attacks. From the output of the targeted machine learning pattern, training data are generated by model inversion (recovering training data). An attacker can request and attack the API of an ML model to obtain the result of predictions. Attacks reproduce identical models by extracting model parameters from them, also called model extraction (disclosing the architecture) and membership attacks (exploiting the model output) [171]. Model inversion attacks could also be a source of privacy violation in 5G and B5G-based networks.
- **Physical attacks:** The infrastructure was aimed at interfering with communication, causing deliberate outages, and altering the communication and computer infrastructure to make decisions and process data. These physical attacks can shut down the entire AI system [124].
- **Privacy Attack:** AI system has the potential to analyze large amounts of data in conjunction with high-speed computers and automation, which is a privacy concern in 5G and B5G based systems [124].
- **GenAI-enabled attacks:** The malicious use of GenAI applications, particularly large language models (LLMs) and diffusion models, poses a significant threat in the realm of cybersecurity. These malicious applications and LLM models can create hyper-realistic deep fakes and impersonate content [172], which facilitate network spoofing, social engineering, and phishing attacks, enabling the deceptive tactics against the network operator and automated agents [173].
- **Automation of cyber-attacks:** Unlike the traditional cyber system, cyber-attacks based on LLMs are autonomous, scalable, stealthy, and faster. The LLMs can be exploited to automate the different stages of cyberattacks, including reconnaissance, discovery of vulnerability, and malware code generation. This ability enables to launch of the most sophisticated attacks on the critical network assets of B5G networks. Existing state-of-the-art tools like FraudGPT and WormGPT are the prime examples of how LLMs can be modified for the use of malicious purposes, thus enabling the creation of malware and facilitating the execution of complex cyberattacks [174].

7.2. AI-enabled security solutions for 5G and B5G networks

To address the Rq-3, we have provided a review of different supervised, unsupervised, and semi-supervised studies for anomaly detection in future wireless networks concerning the three layers of the architecture. Apart from ML, the DL model can help various B5G technologies, including m-MIMO and beamforming. The DL methods can also provide big data security support to the B5G E2E system, which includes cross-layer optimization such as optimizing channel coding, synchronization, and estimations.

Secure communication and random key generation are of utmost importance in the physical layer, also referred to as Physical Layer Security (PLS). The physical layer suffers from authentication issues due to the propagation of communication channel conditions, authentication issues, and interferences. Ken St. Germain and Frank Kragh [175] proposed a supervised deep-learning scheme for the security of the mobile physical layer using a recurrent neural network and CSI to

authenticate the decision. Another study [176] has been conducted to detect jamming attacks in wireless communication networks using reinforcement learning (RL). The study considers the scenario in which an attacker hinders or jams the communication whenever it detects the Zigbee transmission by utilizing the RL algorithm incorporated with a deep neural network (DNN) to learn the optimal policy for the transmission of decoy packets, which are used to obfuscate the real data traffic and to confuse the attacker, in the presence of a jamming attack. The simulation results show that the decoy packet strategy is twice as good for the detection of jamming attacks as compared to the random packet sending strategy. DRL-based solutions [167] can also be adopted in securing of physical layer to mitigate the vulnerabilities related to privacy and physical threats imposed by the complex nature and diverse applications.

Table 7 provides a review of different AI-based solutions available for the detection and identification of attacks in the B5G network. For simplicity, we have classified the different threats and respective AI-based solutions concerning the layers of the architecture. At the network layer, AI enhances security solutions' performance in predicting network attacks [177], filtering malicious traffic, and making intelligent recommendations for network changes. Several performance metrics have been used to validate the effectiveness of the AI-enabled solutions, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F-score. The information on different performance metrics was mentioned in Table 7 about the detection and mitigation of threats in 5G and B5G-based networks. These metrics help assess how the system detects anomalies and abnormal behavior in traffic and classify normal traffic accurately. The most common attack in the network layer is the DoS/DDoS related to the security of SDN, NFV, and network slicing. SD-WAN can benefit from ML algorithms like decision trees, random forests, and support vector machines (SVMs). They can be employed in the SDN environment to detect DDoS attacks [178]. A. Sebbar et al. [179] proposed a context-based node acceptance (CBNA-RF) based random forest for the detection and prevention of MITM attacks in the SDN environment. In [180], the author has utilized an SDN/NFV-based framework for the detection of DDoS attacks using DL algorithm, specifically the LSTM model. A. Elmajed et al. [181] utilizes different ML classifiers, including random forest and XGBOOST for the identification of different anomalies in NFV. The proposed approach achieved an accuracy of more than 90%. In the context of security of network slice, Y. Shi et al. [182] utilized the reinforcement learning algorithm to detect jamming attacks in network slicing of RAN. M. A. Rahman and M. S. Hossain [42] proposed a deep learning-assisted software-defined-security (SDS) architecture that utilized the security function virtualization (SFV) to detect the attacks that occurred due to the convergence of IT and OT in B5G. The author has utilized a mixture of supervised (Recurrent neural network (LSTM)) and unsupervised (Restricted Boltzmann machine (RBM)) DL models for the detection of ransomware and malware attacks.

Finally, in the service layer, AI is a favored technique in different aspects, such as access behavior modeling, or biometric authentication [186]. As highlighted in existing literature the poisoning attack seems critical or life-threatening and need special attention due to the involvement of sensitive data. In [187], the study proposed an independent method for the conduct of a poisoning attack and validated their approach using different ML algorithms and different datasets in healthcare. The study demonstrated that the countermeasure of the attacks can be done by tracking and detecting the deviations in various accuracy metrics to mitigate the impact of the attack.

The study mentioned in [185] proposed a machine-learning technique using XGboost to detect false data injection attacks in IoMT frameworks. This technique aims to enhance the security of the IoMT devices and to protect patient data from malicious manipulation. In the field of autonomous drones, J. Marin [184] has proposed a neural network-based defense system for the detection, identification, and neutralization of drone attacks against unauthorized access. In [188],

the author has combined two approaches: an unsupervised DL approach, an autoencoder, to reconstruct the traffic features, and a supervised DL approach, a deep neural network, as a classifier to detect the abnormal behavior of the traffic. Moreover, the study has incorporated the supervised learning approach, the k-means clustering algorithm, for predicting attacks.

A significant factor in ML Models is the 'Explainability' and 'Interpretability' of the classifier's predictions. Currently, the research is focused on finding those ML models that are both accurate as well as interpretable. This is a complex and challenging task. The main problem with the existing ML/DL models is; either they are interpretable and less accurate, or the existing models are accurate but not interpretable. The decision made by the deep learning models is not interpretable in the sense that neither do they provide sufficient information about which specific features lead to a particular outcome, nor are they explainable to the persons affected by these decisions. Therefore, there is a need to have an efficient ML model that could be both accurate and interpretable at the same time.

Explainable AI (XAI) techniques such as LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanation) and SHAP (Shapley Additive exPlanations) are used in ongoing research to enhance the transparency and trustworthiness of AI-based security solutions by providing valuable and measurable insights into influential factors and their effects on network intrusion predictions. This addresses challenges related to the explainability and interpretability inherent in traditional ML/DL frameworks [189]. Specifically, LIME is used to explain local models and can interpret predictions from any deep learning model. Conversely, SHAP provides a global explanation of model behavior and is used in feature selection to improve model performance [190]. One disadvantage of SHAP is that explaining a prediction for a new instance requires access to the training data to compute each feature's contribution. Another study mentioned in [191] highlights the collection of specific features, such as "destination port" and "packet length", to provide insights into the model's decision-making process in Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS). In their research, the authors used LIME and SHAP to identify these key features, which play a crucial role in understanding and responding to cybersecurity threats.

Moreover, many advanced applications, such as autonomous vehicles and smart cities, rely on the robustness of 5G networks. Fault tolerance and Quantum cryptography solve many security problems for 5G and B5G networks; however, they may not solve all the issues undermining them. In [192], the authors employed a hybrid feature selection approach to identify the most relevant features for anomaly detection. This method helps ensure the system can effectively recognize and respond to faults, thereby enhancing tolerance. To assess the effectiveness of their approach, the authors have utilized the 5G-SliciNdd dataset for effective training and testing of fault detection models. The result demonstrated that the selected approach enhances the system's ability to tolerate faults by preparing it for real-world scenarios. Moreover, a significant work is ongoing on the quantum resilient algorithms for the proactive security of future mobile networks against quantum attacks. Post-quantum cryptography (PQC), a practical demonstration, employs quantum key distribution (QKD) to provide security in 5G and B5G-based networks.

In the B5G network, particularly the B5G edge-of-the-thing (EoT), the authors in [193] proposed a digital-twin-empowered smart attack detection using dynamic feature selection. By leveraging the digital twin and edge computing, the study utilizes the long-short memory autoencoder (LSTM-AE) to improve the security of the IoT environment and to address the growth of increasing attack surfaces in the EoT networks. In another study mentioned in [194], the author has established a meshed topology with QKD networks to ensure resilience against the DoS attack. In this type of network, the secret key is distributed among multiple paths. This means that even if one path is compromised, the key can still be securely transmitted through the alternative routers, ensuring continuous key availability and integrity.

Table 7
Review of different supervised, unsupervised, DL, and DRL solutions.

Layer	Attack category	Ref.	Focus	ML and DL model	Algorithm	Performance metrics
Physical Layer	Authentication	[175]	DL model for the authentication of the physical layer	Supervised DL model	RNN with two variations of conditional generative adversarial network	Accuracy 96.2% Accuracy 90.9%
	Malware and Ransomware	[42]	DL models for the OT defense mechanism	Supervised DL, Un-Supervised DL model	RBM, LSTM, and RNN	Accuracy >95% on multiple datasets
	Privacy and physical attack	[167]	Focus on the vulnerability imposed by the diverse nature of devices	Reinforcement learning	DRL	N/A
	Jamming attack	[176]	Reinforcement learning in wireless communication networks	Reinforcement learning, Supervised DL	RL,DNN	Performance is measured on throughput 0.75kB/slot and the probability of sending a decoy is approx.1for the duration of the simulation
Connection Layer	MITM	[179]	Context-based node acceptance-based random forest in SDN environment	Supervised ML	Random Forest	Precision 99%, Recall 97%, F1-score 98%
	DDoS	[180]	Detection of DDoS attack in SDN/NFV	Unsupervised DL, Reinforcement learning	LSTM, RL	Using the RL system response to block was malicious flows below 40 s.mean response time is of 30.80 s
	Anomalies	[181]	Detection of anomalies and fault detection in NFV	Unsupervised ML Supervised ML	Random forest, xgboost	RF (Precision 93%, Recall 94%, AUC 99%), XGBOOST (Precision 93%, Recall 93%, AUC 91%)
	DDoS	[39]	Detection of DDoS attacks in network slicing	Unsupervised DL	DL-based bidirectional LSTM	Accuracy 99.99%, AUC 99.99%, Precision 99.99%, Recall 99.88%, F1 score 99.99%
	Jamming attack	[182]	Detection of jamming attack in network sling of RAN	Reinforcement learning	RL	Recovery time 986, Maximum reduction in reward 0.536, total reduction 266.581
Application layer	Adversarial Attack	[183]	The detection of adversarial attacks in adaptive traffic control system	Reinforcement learning	DRL	Average Waiting Time, Throughput, Average Queue Length, Average Speed, Carbon Emissions were being used to evaluate the system
	Malicious attacks	[184]	Identification and detection of malicious drone	Supervised ML	DNN	Accuracy of >90%
	False data injection	[185]	Detection of false data injection attack in IoMT	Supervised ML	XGboost	Accuracy 93.7% (10 Fold), ROC 91.8%

QKD is a key agreement and does not provide authentication, digital signatures, or digital certificates [195]. Now, the research is going to jointly use the QKD and PQC in 5G and B5G networks to enable a quantum-safe network.

8. Summary and limitations

In existing state-of-the-art, a couple of studies have been conducted on the classification and modeling of threats in 5G and B5G/6G networks. In this study, we have characterized and modeled the attacks in 5G private networks and beyond. Detailed information on 5G private and B5G network threats has been presented in Sections 4 and 5 respectively. The classification and modeling of the attack have been presented in Section 4.2 and Section 5.2, respectively. To recap;

- RQ-1: What are the known threats associated with 5G private networks?

In this study, we have provided a review of different threats in 5G private network architecture and key technologies influencing these threats. The most common attacks on the 5G private network include the DoS, MITM, interception, and DNS spoofing-based attacks. The study provides the categorization of different types of attack, entry points, and their respective impact on the security requirements are already highlighted in Section 4.2. However, the study is limited to

providing more specific attacks on 5G private networks, such as RAN to core, Core to automation, service platform, and risks to the different applications in 5G private networks. Moreover, the study is limited to providing the impact of attacks on different components and services involved in each architecture layer.

- RQ-2: What are the known threats associated with the key technologies in B5G/6G networks?

In this study, we examine security from two angles: first, by analyzing different threats that impact security requirements, and second, by reviewing the key technologies influencing these threats. To establish this characterization and model, a Hexa-x E2E architecture and a 6G IoT-enabled architecture are used, incorporating the layers—perception, connection, and application layers, respectively.

The perception layer is mainly related to the interference in channel state and random key generation. The broadcast nature of wireless channels is related to adversarial attacks, eavesdropping, and jamming attacks [96]. Random key generation faces different threats in the physical layer of B5G/6G architecture, including passive eavesdropping, injection attacks, and jamming attacks [97]. The connection layer is vulnerable to different threats ranging from topology leakage attacks, botnets, DoS/DDoS, and physical attacks to software, network slicing theft, and misconfiguration attacks. The application layer is responsible for running different types of B5G applications and providing the services to the end user. Typical examples of threats include

jamming, DoS, malware, spoofing, and API-based attacks. The detailed discussion is presented in Section 5.2.

The study is limited in providing information on different attack groups associated with different types of attacks.

This Rq provides a comprehensive view of emerging threats in B5G/6G-based networks, emphasizing the need for a structural approach to threat modeling that considers the layered architecture and various key enablers involved. This understanding is crucial for developing effective security measures to protect the infrastructure against these evolving threats. In addition, a limited number of attack scenarios related to 5G and B5G networks are presented in this study. There is a need to have a security analysis that will provide more information about the attack scenario and vulnerability information in 5G and B5G networks.

- RQ-3: How does AI play as a potential solution in preserving the privacy and security of 5G and B5G-based networks?

Section 7.2 lists different AI-based solutions using different supervised, semi-supervised, and unsupervised ML approaches to secure 5G and B5G networks. Also, solutions exist that use a mixture of supervised and unsupervised methods. The use of AI can identify patterns and forecast future trends in the data. In this way, they are considered a powerful tool for granting system security.

The majority of the solutions work with both 5G and B5G networks. However, some solutions exist that work well with the traditional 5G networks but perform poorly with B5G and 6G networks. For example, IDS solutions work fine with the 5G networks but fail to detect attacks in complex networks. Moreover, it is unclear whether the security solution available for 5 G-based SDN networks works well on SD-WAN. Furthermore, whether the solution available for the network slicing works well or not for the deep slicing and sub-networks in B5G/6G is unclear. Moreover, cyber security attacks in 6G networks are dynamic, polymorphic, sophisticated, use previously unseen custom code, are able to communicate with external command and control, and have entities to update their functionality. B5G/6G technology uses digital twins to predict attacks before they happen to the 6 G-based infrastructure. So, there is a need to explore new solutions, including Generative AI (GenAI) and large language models (LLMs), to provide more robust security solutions to the 5G and 6G networks.

By understanding the innate and realistic data distribution, GenAI can enhance anomaly detection. The application of GenAI generates synthetic traffic patterns that mimic regular traffic usage. The self-learning ability of the GenAI model [196] can autonomously adjust and improve the security of B5G networks. In addition, a class of AI models known as LLM (large language model) can also be utilized to identify and mitigate security threats. With time, these LLM models can adjust to and pick up the updated knowledge from emerging threats and threat models. Furthermore, LLM (large language model) models (a group of AI models) can also be used to identify and mitigate potential threats. These models can adapt to and learn from the new threats and attack vectors over time. It can also adapt to and learn from new threats and attack vectors over time through the ICL (In-Context Learning) feature of LLM. ICT is a unique feature of LLM that allows LLMs to update their knowledge based on the context provided during the interaction, making them flexible and responsive to evolving threats.

Regarding the usage of AI-based solutions, General DATA Protection Regulation (GDPR) plays a critical role in shaping the implications for AI accountability. The individual must take responsibility for choices and the decisions made by the AI system, ensuring that the AI's ethical considerations are integrated into the design and deployment of AI technologies. According to the principle of GDPR, data minimization is mandatory; this principle requires that AI systems in use must utilize the minimum amount of personal data for their intended use. GDPR also emphasizes data accountability by maintaining all records of data processing activities. Moreover, it also encourages monitoring the AI

systems for biases and errors to foster fairness and help mitigate the discriminatory practices of AI decision-making. Furthermore, ethical, legal, and social impacts (ELSI) of the AI system are interconnected and require a comprehensive analysis to ensure that AI technologies are developed and deployed in according with the ethical and societal values.

9. Conclusion & future directions

In the first part, we have included a list of future directions to extend this study and how may expand the threat modeling. In the second subsection, we have summarized the findings of this study.

9.1. Future directions

This study has provided some future research directions that are presented as follows;

- The layered approach can be improved by adding it to the behavior of threats after the deployment of 6G technology and to see the impact of attacks qualitatively or quantitatively on different B5G/6G components.
- Threat modeling can be extended by mapping the identified threats in 5G and B5G-based networks with publicly available databases like MITRE ATT & CK, Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification (CAPEC), and known weakness databases related to Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE).
- The study has focused on the identification and modeling of threats; this analysis can be enhanced by adding information about vulnerabilities for each type of attack using NIST and other standards.
- Threat modeling approach can be enhanced with the graph-based threat modeling, in which nodes can represent the assets and components involved in each layer of the architecture, and edges to model the interdependencies and possible attack paths adopted by the threat actor.
- In the future, there is a need to analyze more specialized security solutions that leverage GenAI and LLM models in DL and FL-based paradigms since the B5G and 6G networks contain a more complex architecture, diverse data sources, and heterogeneous resources.

9.2. Conclusion

The survey provided an overview of different research efforts and projects for the development and building of 5G and B5G-based networks. Different research challenges are involved in 5G and B5G networks. Among them, security is one of the main issues. Other issues are related to the availability, latency, reliability, data rates, and performance of the networks. The survey's main focus is to review the different security threats in 5G private and B5G networks. Different open-source RAN and open-source core solutions are proposed in the existing state of the art for the development of 5G private networks. The details of these open-source tools are provided in this survey. 5G networks are also used to provide support to the different key enabling technologies; these key technologies are associated with various security risks and cyberattacks. The range of the attacks on 5G private networks is from RAN to core, air interface, API, and automation attacks. It is expected that future wireless technology will adopt many concepts from the 5G technologies, along with providing support to the diverse use cases. To meet the primary focus of this research, we have adopted a baseline architecture from the industrial use case of 5G private networks. In the first step, we have identified the threats associated with RAN, API, key enabling, and communication technologies involved. Then we have classified the different attacks under a single category, and finally, the classification and modeling of threats have

been done using the adopted layered architecture. The infrastructure of the B5G network provides an open network platform and open interface, and a more complex architecture compared to 5G. Due to the heterogeneous nature of B5G networks and support for diverse use cases, it is also exposed to various security risks and attacks. The range of these attacks is from communication and signaling attacks to interception and manipulation attacks. Similarly, in the analysis of 5G private networks, we have analyzed the identified different threats in B5G/6G networks and key enabling technologies, classified the threats under the same category, and provided the classification and modeling of threats with a baseline architecture of Hexa-x end-to-end. To overcome the threats in 5G and B5G networks, AI plays a vital role in preserving the privacy and security of the network. This study also provides an overview of different AI-enabled solutions related to ML, DL, and FL for preserving the privacy and security of 5G and B5G networks. Moreover, the details of different classical and 5G-specific datasets are also provided that add value to the identification and prediction of attacks in 5G and B5G-based networks. While using AI as a decision-making system in various domains, it is also important to ensure the responsible deployment of AI in 5G and B5G networks by evaluating the ethical, legal, and social impacts that require delicate handling. The key areas include accountability and transparency of AI systems, ethical implications of AI on privacy and security, the potential for AI to reinforce pre-existing biases and discrimination, and the responsibility of both individuals and developers to ensure that AI is employed ethically and responsibly. Businesses that implement the XAI techniques not only fulfill the requirements of regulatory bodies such as the General DATA Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) but also gain the user trust via a transparent decision-making process. For example, in the financial sector, XAI is integrated into credit scoring models to comply with GDPR requirements while ensuring fairness and transparency in lending decision-making. On the other hand, CCPA does not require businesses to explain how AI makes the decision, like GDPR does. However, it strongly focuses on protecting the rights of consumers, especially how the personal data is utilized within AI applications and whether they have given permission for that use. Concluding that, this review helps in providing useful insights into the selection of specific classifiers for the different types of attacks in their mitigation and prevention of B5G infrastructure.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Saman Tariq: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Eva Rodriguez Luna:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Xavier Masip Bruin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Rodrigo Diaz:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Josep Martrat:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Panagiotis Trakadas:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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